

**Assessing the Impact of Climate Change on Lake Gregory
Surface Water Temperature Using the General Lake Model
(GLM) and Satellite-Derived Data**

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M.Sc.Eng.

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This thesis has been submitted to the University of Peradeniya as a partial fulfilment of the requirements for the Degree of Master of the Science of Engineering.

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the work presented in this thesis is the result of my own investigation and that it has not been submitted in candidature for a degree/diploma of this or any other university.

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ABSTRACT

Lake Gregory is a small, shallow lake (0.4 km², 2.58 m depth) located in Nuwara Eliya, Sri Lanka, surrounded by an urban landscape. The Lake Surface Water Temperature (LSWT) plays a crucial role in the lake's energy budget yet has not been well understood due to the lack of reliable ground measurements. This study aims to bridge this gap by developing a one-dimensional hydrodynamic model using the General Lake Model (GLM) to simulate daily LSWT from 2017 to 2021. NASA POWER reanalysis data was utilized as the primary meteorological input.

Calibration and validation of the GLM were conducted using Landsat Level 2 Surface Temperature Science Product (LST-L2) data from the USGS and NASA, due to the unavailability of reliable LSWT measurements. The GLM demonstrated good performance, achieving Root Mean Square Errors (RMSE) of 2.15°C and 2.17°C, and correlation coefficients of 0.65 during calibration and validation, respectively. The overall performance across both phases yielded an RMSE of 2.02°C and a correlation coefficient of 0.73, underscoring the model's accuracy in simulating LSWT.

The study revealed a strong correlation between NASA POWER reanalysis data and observed precipitation, though with tendencies to overestimate and underestimate during specific periods. The Northeast Monsoon (NEM) season displayed high accuracy, while lower accuracy was noted during the Second Inter-Monsoon (SIM) period. Bias correction applied to NASA POWER air temperature data significantly improved correlation,

addressing discrepancies linked to scaling factors. Wind speed, relative humidity, and cloud cover data from NASA POWER exhibited strong correlations with observed values, further validating the reliability of the reanalysis data.

This study investigates the impacts of climate variability on lake surface temperature deviations, focusing on the interplay of key climatic factors such as air temperature, solar radiation, and wind speed. Using the General Lake Model (GLM), 256 unique climatic scenarios were analysed, incorporating variations in air temperature (+5°C, +2.5°C, -2.5°C, -5°C), solar radiation (+50%, +25%, -25%, -50%), wind speed (+50%, +25%, -25%, -50%), and rainfall (+50%, +25%, -25%, -50%). Results indicate that the scenario with a 5°C increase in air temperature, 50% increase in solar radiation, 50% decrease in wind speed, and 50% decrease in rainfall drives the highest temperature deviations during most months, with deviations peaking at 11.09°C in April. Correlation analyses reveal a strong relationship between temperature deviations and wind speed (-0.87), underscoring its critical role in modulating lake surface warming. Seasonal analysis demonstrates that reduced wind speeds amplify warming across all seasons, highlighting their significance in shaping lake thermal responses. These findings emphasize the importance of integrating adaptive, season-specific lake management strategies to address the multifaceted impacts of climate variability on aquatic ecosystems in Lake Gregory.

This study demonstrates the effectiveness of combining satellite-derived LST-L2 data with reanalysis products and hydrodynamic modelling to simulate LSWT, providing valuable

insights into the influence of climate change on small, ungauged lakes like Lake Gregory. The findings also highlight the utility and challenges of employing a satellite-driven GLM for LSWT estimation, emphasizing the importance of globally available data sources for hydrodynamic modelling in ungauged basins.

CONTENTS

DECLARATION.....	i
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	ii
ABSTRACT	iv
CONTENTS	vii
LIST OF FIGURES	xi
LIST OF TABLES	xiii
ABBREVIATIONS	xiv
1. CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1 Background	1
1.1.1. LSWT: A Key Indicator of Climate Impact on Aquatic Ecosystems	1
1.1.2. Traditional Water Temperature Monitoring Challenges in Data-Scarce Regions.....	2
1.1.3. Remote Sensing's Role in Enhancing LSWT Measurement	3
1.1.4. Landsat Data for Enhanced LSWT Measurement	4
1.1.5. General Lake Model (GLM): A Versatile Hydrodynamics Tool	5
1.1.6. GLM and Meteorological Data Challenges	6
1.1.7. NASA POWER Reanalysis Data: A Meteorological Resource	6
1.1.8. Remote Sensing Assessment of Small-Scale Lake Surface Water Temperature: Challenges and Solutions in Data-Scarce Environments	7
1.2 Problem Statement.....	8
1.3 Research Aim and Objectives	10
1.3.1. Aim	10
1.3.2. Objectives:	10
1.4 Scope of the Research	11
2. Chapter 2: Literature Review	14
2.1 Lake Surface water Temperature	14
2.1.1. Ecosystem Impacts	14

2.1.2.	Lake Dynamics	17
2.1.3.	Climate and Mesoscale Meteorology	17
2.2	LSWT Data Scarcity and Remote Sensing Approach.....	21
2.3	LSWT derived from Advanced Very High-Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) 1 km data set.....	23
2.4	LSWT derived from MODIS LST products	25
2.5	Landsat Collection 2 Surface Temperature	26
2.5.1.	Known issues.....	28
2.5.2.	Evaluation of Landsat surface temperature product	29
2.5.3.	Cloud and cloud shadow mask	34
2.6	GLM overview	36
2.6.1.	Layer Structure.....	37
2.6.2.	Water balance.....	39
2.6.3.	Surface energy balance.....	41
2.7	GLM on LSWT.....	43
2.8	NASA Power	50
3.	CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY	52
3.1	Study Area.....	52
3.2	Research Methodology	54
3.3	Acquisition and Processing of Bathymetry Data for Lake Gregory Using Historical Surveys	55
3.4	Landsat Collection 2 surface temperature data processing	57
3.4.1.	Data Downloaded process	57
3.4.2.	The delineated water body of Lake Gregory	62
3.4.3.	Surface temperature data extraction process in ArcMap	66
3.5	NASA Power Data Retrieval	75
3.6	Observed Climatic Data Retrieval	76
3.6.1.	URL Generation.....	76
3.6.2.	Data Scraping	77
3.6.3.	Data Cleaning and Storage.....	78

3.6.4.	Execution.....	78
3.7	Validation metrics	79
3.8	Comparison of NASA POWER Reanalysis Data with Observed Meteorological Data	80
3.9	GLM Setup.....	81
3.9.1.	Overview	81
3.9.2.	Meteorological configuration and met.csv	85
3.10	GLM in R.....	85
3.11	GLM Model Calibration.....	86
4.	CHAPTER 4: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	87
4.1	Evaluating NASA Power Reanalysis Data	87
4.1.1.	Precipitation.....	87
4.1.2.	Average Temperature	93
4.1.3.	Average Wind Speed.....	97
4.1.4.	Average Relative Humidity	100
4.1.5.	Cloud Cover.....	103
4.2	Evaluating Landsat Surface Temperature Product-Derived Lake Surface Temperatures.....	105
4.3	Lake surface temperatures modelled by the General Lake Model (GLM) ...	108
4.3.1.	Sensitivity analysis	108
4.3.2.	Model Calibration and Validation	110
4.4	Climate Change scenarios.....	117
4.4.1.	Introduction	117
4.4.2.	Results.....	119
4.4.3.	Dominant Scenario Patterns	121
4.4.4.	Seasonal Variability and Impacts	122
4.4.5.	Key Climatic Drivers	124
4.4.6.	Implications for Lake Management	125
5.	CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSION AND LIMITATIONS WITH FURTHER STUDIES.....	126
5.1	Conclusion.....	126

5.2	Limitation with further studies	128
6.	REFERENCES	131
ANNEX 01	135
ANNEX 02	138
ANNEX 03	141
ANNEX 04	147
ANNEX 05	173

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 2. 1: Landsat 9 Surface Reflectance RGB composite (Bands 4,3,2) (left) and the corresponding colour-enhanced Surface Temperature (right) (Landsat, 2022).....	27
Figure 2. 2: ASTER Global Emissivity Dataset 100-meter HDF5 V003 for Study Area, footprint (Right) Corresponding colour enhanced Emissivity Dataset (Left).....	29
Figure 2. 3: Example validation of the Collection 2 Landsat 8 surface temperature products for land sites (left) and lake sites (right) derived from hundreds of cloud-free acquisitions acquired 2018–2021 (Crawford et al., 2023).....	34
Figure 2. 4: Schematic of a GLM simulation domain, input information (blue text) and key simulated processes (black text) (Hipsey et al., 2019).....	41
Figure 2. 5: Location of Lake Chaohu at the Anhui Province in China, sampling sites for water temperature (Zhang et al., 2020).	45
Figure 3. 1: Lake Gregory	53
Figure 3. 2: Research Methodology	55
Figure 3. 3: Survey conducted by the Sri Lanka Land Development Corporation in 1988 ..	56
Figure 3. 4: develop a detailed bathymetry map of Lake Gregory	57
Figure 3. 5: Search criteria in USGS earth explore	58
Figure 3. 6: Data Set	58
Figure 3. 7: Clear sky image over Lake Gregory Dated 2021.12.26	59
Figure 3. 8: Cloud Covered Image Over Lake Gregory Dated 2021.10.23	60
Figure 3. 9: Produced tile after using Composite band tool	62
Figure 3. 10: unsupervised cluster classification	63
Figure 3. 11: Reclassified image	64
Figure 3. 12: Extracted surrounding area of Lake Gregory	64
Figure 3. 13: Extracted Raster of Lake Gregory	65
Figure 3. 14: Extracted shape file of Lake Gregory	66
Figure 3. 15: Model for Surface Temperature and Extract by Lake Area	68
Figure 3. 16: Model for Surface Temperature Uncertainty and Extract by Lake Area	68
Figure 3. 17: Model for combining Surface Temperature Uncertainty as point files	70
Figure 3. 18: LC08_L2SP_141055_20170318_20200904_02_T1_QA_PIXEL.TIF.tif.....	73
Figure 3. 19: Model for Extract water pixel temperatures from Temperature point files that include both uncertainty and ST	74
Figure 3. 20: Flow diagram showing the files required for operation of the Model configuration & parameters: glm.nml	82

Figure 4. 1: Average monthly Observed Precipitation vs NASA power Precipitation data	.88
Figure 4. 2: Seasonal Comparison of Monthly Observed Precipitation and NASA Power Precipitation Data89
Figure 4. 3: Monthly Comparison of Monthly Observed Precipitation and NASA Power Precipitation Data92
Figure 4. 4: Average monthly Observed Temperature vs NASA power Temperature Data	93
Figure 4. 5: Scatter plot of Observed average Temperatures and NASA Power Bias corrected average temperature values from 2009 to 202195
Figure 4. 6: Monthly Comparison of Monthly Observed Average Temperatures and NASA Power Bias Corrected Average Temperatures96
Figure 4. 7: Average monthly Observed Wind Speed vs NASA power Wind Speed97
Figure 4. 8: Scatter plot of monthly Observed average Wind Speed and NASA Power Wind Speed values from 2009 to 202198
Figure 4. 9: Monthly Comparison of Monthly Observed Average Wind Speed and NASA Power Wind Speed99
Figure 4. 10: Average monthly Observed RH vs NASA RH100
Figure 4. 11: Scatter plot of monthly Observed average RH and NASA Power RH values from 2009 to 2021101
Figure 4. 12: Monthly Comparison of Monthly Observed Average Relative Humidity and NASA Power Relative Humidity102
Figure 4. 13: Monthly Observed Average Cloud Cover and NASA Power Cloud Cover103
Figure 4. 14: Scatter plot of monthly Observed average Cloud Cover and NASA Power Cloud Cover values from 2017 to 2020104
Figure 4. 15: Temperature comparison of 4 different weather stations (Darman et al., 2024)105
Figure 4. 16: Optimization Using CMA-ES For Temperature112
Figure 4. 17: Calibrated GLM simulation (Black Line) of LST and Landsat LST (Red Dots)	.114
Figure 4. 18: Calibrated GLM simulation (Black Line) of LST and Measured water temperatures by Department of Irrigation (Red Dots)114
Figure 4. 19: Calibrated GLM simulation (Black Line) of LST, Measured water temperatures by Department of Irrigation (Brown Dots), Landsat LST (Red Dots) and outflow (Blue line)116
Figure 4. 20: GLM simulation of Temperature Variations117
Figure 4. 21: Monthly Average Surface Water Temperature variation for all scenarios	..120
Figure 4. 22: Climatic scenarios with the maximum lake surface temperature deviations (Compared to baseline condition)121
Figure 4. 23: Relationship between Wind Speed and Maximum Lake Surface Temperature Deviations125

LIST OF TABLES

Table 2. 1: Landsat Collection 2 Level 1 and Level 2 per-pixel quality assessment (QA) (Crawford et al., 2023)	32
Table 2. 2: Atmospheric auxiliary data ingest for Landsat Collection 2 Level 2 product generation. (Crawford et al., 2023).....	33
Table 3. 1: Landsat Product Identifier (Landsat, 2022)	61
Table 3. 2: Landsat 8-9 Pixel Quality Assessment (QA_PIXEL) Bit Index (Crawford et al., 2023)	71
Table 3. 3: Landsat 8-9 Pixel Quality Assessment (QA_PIXEL) Value Interpretations	73
Table 4. 1: Temperature Bias Correction	94
Table 4. 2: Landsat Surface Temperature Product Derived Lake Surface Temperatures..	106
Table 4. 3: Sensitivity Analysis	109
Table 4. 4: Calibration Parameters.....	111
Table 4. 5: Calibrated Final Parameters	112

ABBREVIATIONS

AAE: Anaerobic Aerobic Epilimnion

ASTER: Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer

AVHRR: Advanced Very High-Resolution Radiometer

BT: Brightness Temperature

CDEM: Canadian Digital Elevation Model

CEB: Ceylon Electricity Board

CFSR: Climate Forecast System Reanalysis

COG: Cloud Optional GeoTIFF

DEM: Digital Elevation Model

DYRESM: Dynamic Reservoir Simulation Model

ECMWF: European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts

ETOPO5: Earth Topography Five-Minute Grid

FIM: First Inter-monsoon

Flake: Fresh Shallow Water Lake Model

FP-IT: Forward Processing for Instrument Teams

GED: Global Emissivity Dataset

GIMP: Greenland Ice Mapping Project

GIS: Geographic Information System

GLS: Global Land Survey

GLEON: Global Lake Ecological Observatory Network

GLM: General Lake Model

IFS: Integrated Forecasting System

IT: Instrument Teams

IwbST: Inland Water Body Surface Temperature

LaSRC: Land Surface Reflectance Code

LPDAAC: Land Processes Distributed Archive Centre
LST-L2: Level-2 Surface Temperature Science Product
LSWT: Lake Surface Water Temperature
MERRA-2: Modern-Era Retrospective Analysis for Research and Application Version 2
MetOP-A: Meteorological Operational Polar Satellite – A
MODIS: Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
MODTRAN: MODerate resolution atmospheric TRANsmission
NASADEM: NASA Shuttle Radar Topography Mission
NCEP: National Centres for Environmental Prediction
NDSI: Normalized Difference Snow Index
NDVI: Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
NED: National Elevation Dataset for Alaska
NEM: Northeast-monsoon
NPI: Norwegian Polar Institute
NOAA: National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
OLI: Operational Land Imager
QA: Quality Assessment
RTTOV: Radiative Transfer TOVS
SIM: Second Inter-monsoon
SNF: Sweden, Norway, and Finland National Elevation Data
SST: Sea Surface Temperature
ST: Surface Temperature
SWIR: Short Wave Infrared
SWM: Southwest-monsoon
TES: Temperature Emissivity Separation
TIR: Thermal Infrared
TOA: Top of Atmosphere

TRIS: Thermal Infrared Sensor

VNIR: Visible Near Infrared

WRS: Worldwide Reference System

1. CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

1.1.1. LSWT: A Key Indicator of Climate Impact on Aquatic Ecosystems

Water temperature exerts a profound influence on various aspects of aquatic ecosystems, encompassing organism metabolism and the activities of bacteria and algae. Notably, alterations in water temperature can disrupt the equilibrium of an aquatic ecosystem, influence species composition, and even impact trophic conditions. Furthermore, water temperature exerts a critical role in governing essential processes within lakes, such as thermal stratification and mixing dynamics (Lieberherr & Wunderle, 2018). The thermal regime of a lake is primarily governed by the exchange of heat at the interface between air and water. Within this context, Lake Surface Water Temperature (LSWT) emerges as a pivotal factor in regulating the intricate heat exchange processes (Tetzlaff, 1979).

Recent decades have unveiled a notable trend: LSWT tends to warm at a faster rate compared to the corresponding ambient air temperature. This phenomenon underscores the lake's responsiveness to the forces of climate change, making changes in lake water temperature a conspicuous indicator of broader environmental shifts (Jia et al., 2022). Consequently, LSWT assumes significance as an essential climatic variable meriting continuous monitoring (Adrian et al., 2009). In light of its multifaceted implications for

aquatic ecosystems and its potential as a barometer of regional climate change, the monitoring of LSWT assumes paramount importance.

1.1.2. Traditional Water Temperature Monitoring Challenges in Data-Scarce Regions

Traditionally, the measurement of water temperature has relied on in-situ thermometers, which are deployed either manually or using automated recording stations. These measurements are conducted at various specific locations within the water body, with intervals and depths chosen based on the specific objectives of research organizations or institutes. However, the endeavour to maintain a consistent and frequent regimen of in-situ Lake Surface Water Temperature (LSWT) measurements demands a substantial allocation of human labour and technical resources. This challenge becomes particularly pronounced in underdeveloped nations like Sri Lanka, where most of the multitude of lakes remain devoid of long-term LSWT datasets.

The lack of comprehensive and sustained LSWT measurements in such regions poses a significant obstacle to understanding long-term variations in lake temperature and their responses to climate change. Consequently, there is a growing need to develop methodologies that enable the extension of historical LSWT time series, thus facilitating a more comprehensive assessment of how lakes have responded to environmental shifts over time (Lieberherr & Wunderle, 2018; Zhang et al., 2020).

1.1.3. Remote Sensing's Role in Enhancing LSWT Measurement

Remote sensing presents an enticing approach to complement traditional temperature measurements due to its capability to provide data with high spatiotemporal resolution. Unlike in-situ measurements, remote sensing, typically conducted via satellite-based sensors, does not offer the same level of accuracy at a single point in space. Instead, it furnishes a grid of temperature measurements, each aggregated over specific areas of the lake's surface according to the sensor's resolution.

Recent research findings highlight the promise of remote sensing for Lake Surface Water Temperature (LSWT) assessment. For instance, a study by (Zhang et al., 2020) demonstrated that LSWT derived from MODIS data exhibited a strong correlation with actual lake surface temperature variations, with a correlation coefficient of 0.96. Although there was a slight cool bias of 1.25, the overall agreement between the remote sensing data and actual temperature variations was noteworthy.

Another study (Lieberherr & Wunderle, 2018) focused on European lakes and employed data from the Advanced Very High-Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) sensor for LSWT calculations. Furthermore, the Along Track Scanning Radiometer (ATSR) series (Woolway & Merchant, 2018) has been instrumental in investigating the impacts of climate change on LSWT for Large Northern Hemisphere Lakes.

While MODIS, AVHRR, and ATSR products offer commendable temporal resolution, they are limited by their spatial resolution, typically exceeding 1 km. Consequently, they are less

suitable for measuring the temperature of lakes falling within the smallest size class, typically ranging from 0.1 to 1 km². These limitations in spatial resolution must be considered when selecting the most appropriate remote sensing tools for LSWT assessment.

1.1.4. Landsat Data for Enhanced LSWT Measurement

The Landsat Level 2 Surface Temperature Science Product data offer a valuable alternative for measuring Lake Surface Water Temperature (LSWT) in smaller lakes, given its spatial resolution of 30 meters (Dyba et al., 2022). This level of detail is particularly advantageous for monitoring small-scale lakes where finer spatial resolution is essential for accurate temperature assessments. However, it is important to note that Landsat's temporal resolution is somewhat limited, operating on a 16-day cycle.

One of the challenges encountered when using Landsat data for LSWT measurement is the presence of cloud cover, which can obstruct observations during certain periods of the 16-day cycle. This limitation can affect data acquisition and may result in incomplete LSWT records for specific time intervals.

A study conducted by (Dyba et al., 2022) has addressed these considerations by examining the applicability of Landsat Level 2 Surface Temperature Science Product (LST-L2) data for lakes in Poland. This research likely provides valuable insights into the utilization of Landsat data for LSWT assessment, particularly in regions with characteristics similar to the study area.

1.1.5. General Lake Model (GLM): A Versatile Hydrodynamics Tool

The General Lake Model (GLM) is a notable open-source software tool that operates on a one-dimensional framework within the R programming environment. Its primary function is to simulate the hydrodynamics of inland water bodies (Hipsey et al., 2019). What sets GLM apart is its capability to strike a favourable balance between computational efficiency and physical realism while imposing minimal calibration demands and requiring fewer input data compared to some other modelling approaches (Zhang et al., 2020).

To assess the performance and applicability of the GLM for Lake Surface Water Temperature (LSWT) simulations, a study conducted by (Zhang et al., 2020) undertook a comprehensive evaluation. This assessment spanned various time scales and encompassed the comparison of GLM-simulated LSWT with two different datasets: in-situ LSWT measurements and LSWT data derived from the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) sensor.

By examining the GLM's performance against these datasets, the study by (Zhang et al., 2020) likely yielded valuable insights into the model's ability to accurately simulate LSWT dynamics across different temporal scales and under varying conditions. Such evaluations are crucial for establishing the reliability and robustness of the GLM as a tool for LSWT assessment.

1.1.6. GLM and Meteorological Data Challenges

The General Lake Model (GLM) offers the potential to replace measurements with higher temporal resolution, which can be particularly advantageous in assessing Lake Surface Water Temperature (LSWT). However, this task hinges on the availability of essential driving data, especially meteorological input data. In Sri Lanka, acquiring the requisite data at the necessary spatial and temporal resolutions can be a formidable challenge. These limitations have raised uncertainties regarding the feasibility of obtaining meteorological input data of sufficient quality using atmospheric models.

Addressing these challenges, (Frassl et al., 2018) conducted a significant investigation into whether coarse meteorological and hydrological data derived from global models could be directly utilized as driving data for lake modelling. The study likely delved into the potential of these global models to provide the necessary meteorological information to drive the GLM with an acceptable degree of accuracy. This research would have critical implications for expanding the applicability of the GLM in regions where fine-scale meteorological data may be scarce or difficult to obtain.

1.1.7. NASA POWER Reanalysis Data: A Meteorological Resource

The NASA Prediction of Worldwide Energy Resource (NASA POWER) reanalysis data constitutes a valuable resource for meteorological information, and it is accessible through the NASA POWER website "<https://power.larc.nasa.gov/>". This dataset is provided at a spatial resolution of 0.5° latitude by 0.5° longitude and encompasses a comprehensive set

of daily meteorological variables, including air temperature, relative humidity, rainfall, solar radiation, wind speed, and cloud cover.

What distinguishes NASA POWER is its derivation from numerical weather prediction model simulations based on a compilation of meteorological observations. This synthesis of data sources results in a dataset that offers a comprehensive and reliable representation of meteorological conditions.

One of the noteworthy aspects of NASA POWER is its accessibility and ease of use. It is available as a single point of access, allowing users to retrieve regional and global daily meteorological data conveniently (Rodrigues & Braga, 2021). This user-friendly aspect makes it a valuable tool for researchers and practitioners seeking meteorological information for various applications, including environmental modelling and assessment.

1.1.8. Remote Sensing Assessment of Small-Scale Lake Surface Water Temperature: Challenges and Solutions in Data-Scarce Environments

The application of remote sensing techniques for the calibration and validation of Lake Surface Water Temperature (LSWT) simulations generated by the General Lake Model (GLM), employing reanalysis data as input, remains a complex and relatively unexplored domain, particularly concerning small-scale lakes. This study aims to comprehensively evaluate the limitations and challenges associated with utilizing Landsat Surface Temperature products and NASA POWER reanalysis data for the simulation of daily LSWT in a data-scarce environment. The focal point of this investigation is Lake Gregory, situated

in the picturesque region of Nuwara Eliya, Sri Lanka. By addressing these challenges, this research seeks to advance the understanding of the applicability of remote sensing in the assessment of LSWT in small-scale lakes and contribute to improved environmental monitoring and management practices.

1.2 Problem Statement

Lake Surface Water Temperature (LSWT) is a vital environmental indicator, crucial for understanding the dynamics of aquatic ecosystems and their response to climate change. However, in many underdeveloped and rural areas, the lack of comprehensive LSWT data hampers its in-depth study and monitoring. This data deficiency poses a significant challenge, particularly in regions like Sri Lanka, where thousands of small lakes remain inadequately monitored for environmental indicators, and there is a pressing need for reliable spatial and temporal resolution data.

To address this knowledge gap and better comprehend LSWT variations in these regions, numerical models like the General Lake Model (GLM) offer a promising avenue. However, a cascade of challenges arises in this endeavour:

1. Absence of Observed Data:

The primary hurdle is the scarcity of observed LSWT data. In many underdeveloped and rural areas, the necessary in-situ measurements are often unavailable or insufficient,

leaving researchers without the critical ground-truth data required to calibrate and validate the GLM or similar models.

2. Lack of Meteorological and Hydrological Data:

To accurately model LSWT, meteorological and hydrological data are essential as input variables. Unfortunately, these data are often missing or inadequately collected, particularly in the required temporal resolution. This scarcity compounds the challenges faced in modelling LSWT accurately.

3. Small-Scale Lake Monitoring:

Sri Lanka, like many other regions, hosts a multitude of small lakes that have not been systematically monitored for environmental indicators. These smaller water bodies are critical components of the local landscape, and understanding their LSWT dynamics is vital, as elaborated in the background of this research. However, their neglect of monitoring exacerbates the overall data deficiency problem.

4. Reliability of Spatial and Temporal Resolution:

Even if data were available, ensuring reliable spatial and temporal resolution remains a challenge. Many monitoring efforts may not provide the granularity required to understand fine-scale variations in LSWT over time.

Considering these challenges, this thesis aims to explore innovative approaches, such as data assimilation techniques, remote sensing, and the integration of available datasets, to

bridge the data gap. By doing so, the research endeavours to advance the understanding of LSWT dynamics in underdeveloped and rural areas, enabling more effective environmental monitoring and management practices.

1.3 Research Aim and Objectives

1.3.1. Aim

To assess the feasibility of developing a daily Lake Surface Water temperature (LSWT) model for Lake Gregory, situated in Nuwara Eliya, Sri Lanka, utilizing the General Lake Model (GLM) with NASA POWER reanalysis data as meteorological driving and evaluate temporal trends in Lake Gregory's surface water temperature.

1.3.2. Objectives:

- To collect and pre-process essential datasets, including NASA POWER reanalysis data, Landsat Level 2 imagery, and additional inputs required for GLM model development of Lake Gregory.
- To implement the General Lake Model (GLM) using a closed-basin approach with NASA POWER reanalysis data as meteorological driving inputs and develop a daily LSWT model for Lake Gregory.
- Evaluate temporal trends in Lake Gregory's surface water temperature (LSWT) by analysing synthetic climate scenarios to identify the most influential meteorological parameters contributing to LSWT increase.

By pursuing these objectives, this thesis aims to contribute to the understanding of LSWT dynamics in Lake Gregory, demonstrate the applicability of the GLM model in data-scarce regions, and offer insights into the feasibility of utilizing remote sensing and reanalysis data for monitoring small-scale lakes in underdeveloped areas.

1.4 Scope of the Research

This research project focuses on the development and evaluation of a daily Lake Surface Water Temperature (LSWT) model for Lake Gregory, located in Nuwara Eliya, Sri Lanka. The study's scope encompasses various key aspects:

1. Geographic Focus:

- The research is specifically centred on Lake Gregory, a prominent water body situated in the region of Nuwara Eliya, Sri Lanka. This choice allows for an in-depth examination of LSWT dynamics in a specific geographic context.

2. Modelling Framework:

- The primary modelling framework employed in this research is the General Lake Model (GLM). GLM offers a robust platform for simulating LSWT and is chosen for its adaptability to data-scarce environments.

3. Data Sources:

- The study leverages NASA POWER reanalysis data as the primary meteorological driving data for the GLM model. This dataset provides essential meteorological

variables, including air temperature, relative humidity, rainfall, solar radiation, wind speed, and cloud cover.

4. Closed-Basin Approach:

- In our simulation, the heat effects of inflows and outflows were disregarded, as previous observations (ANNEX 05) showed that the temperature differences between inflows and outflows were minimal, with no notable variation.

5. Temporal Resolution:

- The research focuses on developing a daily LSWT model. This high temporal resolution allows for the analysis of fine-scale variations in water temperature over time.

6. Calibration and Validation:

- The study aims to calibrate the GLM model, if feasible, using available observed LSWT data. Validation of the model's performance will be conducted against independent datasets, with particular emphasis on utilizing the Landsat Level 2 Surface Temperature Science Product data.

7. Feasibility Assessment:

- An essential component of this research is the assessment of the feasibility of applying the GLM model, NASA POWER reanalysis data, and Landsat imagery in data-scarce environments, such as Lake Gregory in Sri Lanka.

8. Environmental Implications:

- The findings of this study will be discussed in the context of their broader environmental implications. Insights into LSWT dynamics can inform environmental monitoring and management practices in the region.

9. Recommendations and Future Directions:

- The research will conclude with recommendations for further research endeavours and potential enhancements to the modelling approach, contributing to the advancement of LSWT studies in similar data-scarce regions.

By addressing these specific components within the scope of this research, the study seeks to advance the understanding of LSWT dynamics in Lake Gregory and provide valuable insights into modelling approaches, remote sensing, and reanalysis data utilization for monitoring small-scale lakes in underdeveloped areas, potentially paving the way for improved environmental assessments and management practices.

2. Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Lake Surface water Temperature

An important aspect of aquatic habitats is water temperature, which affects a variety of biological and physical processes. In this section, discuss the complex relationship between water temperature and aquatic ecosystems, lake dynamics, and climate change monitoring. It focuses mostly on Lake Surface Water Temperature (LSWT) (Lieberherr & Wunderle, 2018).

2.1.1. Ecosystem Impacts

The studies conducted in the northern Baltic Sea, Kiel Fjord, Shimajigawa reservoir in Japan, and lakes in central Sweden provide valuable insights into the ecosystem impacts of temperature variations on marine and freshwater environments (Müren et al., 2005; Hoppe et al., 2008; Komatsu et al., 2007; Malmaeus et al., 2006). These studies collectively demonstrate the significant influence of temperature on various trophic levels and ecosystem processes, highlighting the complex interactions within aquatic ecosystems.

In the northern Baltic Sea mesocosm studies, it was observed that temperature variations from 5 to 20 °C had profound effects on the marine pelagic food web. The heterotrophic to autotrophic biomass ratio increased significantly with rising temperatures, indicating a shift towards a more heterotrophic ecosystem at higher temperatures. This change in biomass ratio was accompanied by a decrease in the carbon fixation to respiration ratio, suggesting

alterations in the balance between autotrophy and heterotrophy. Additionally, sedimentation rates decreased with increasing temperatures, likely due to increased bacterial biodegradation and respiration losses. These findings underscore the sensitivity of marine ecosystems to temperature changes and the potential implications for ecosystem functioning, especially in temperate regions (Müren et al., 2005).

The mesocosm study in the Kiel Fjord focused on the effects of expected sea surface temperature increases during winter on phytoplankton primary production and bacterial secondary production. The results indicated that rising temperatures did not affect the timing of phytoplankton primary production peaks but led to earlier peaks in bacterial secondary production. The ratio of bacterial secondary production to phytoplankton primary production increased with temperature, suggesting a shift towards enhanced bacterial decomposition of organic matter. This study highlights the intricate relationships between temperature, primary production, and bacterial processes in aquatic ecosystems, emphasizing the potential consequences of temperature changes on nutrient cycling and carbon fluxes (Hoppe et al., 2008).

In the study on the Shimajigawa reservoir in Japan, researchers investigated the long-term effects of global warming on environmental factors and aquatic ecosystems using climate change scenarios. The simulations projected a significant rise in surface water temperatures by the 2090s compared to the 1990s, with an estimated increase of 3.4 °C. Specifically, surface water and hypolimnion temperatures were predicted to increase by

3.8 °C and 2.8 °C, respectively. These temperature elevations were anticipated to deepen the reservoir's thermocline and prolong thermal stratification periods. The increased temperatures were expected to elevate oxygen requirements for aerobic breakdown and facilitate the upward movement of phosphorus from sediments, leading to higher phosphorus concentrations in the hypolimnion. The release of phosphorus from sediments to the anaerobic-anaerobic-epilimnion (AAE) layer through vertical diffusion was projected to stimulate phytoplankton growth in the epilimnion. The long-term projections from the water quality model indicated that trophic lake conditions would deteriorate due to global warming, fostering increased algae growth and significant alterations in aquatic ecosystems (Komatsu et al., 2007).

The study in central Sweden using a lake model and a phosphorus model under different temperature scenarios highlighted the differential responses of lakes to climate warming. Lake Erken, with a longer water residence time, showed a more pronounced increase in epigenetic-dissolved phosphorus concentration and potential for phytoplankton production under a warm climate scenario compared to the Lake Mälaren basins. This suggests that lakes with extended water residence times may experience intensified eutrophication under future climate warming, necessitating proactive management strategies to safeguard water quality (Malmaeus et al., 2006).

2.1.2. Lake Dynamics

The research studies conducted on Lake Constance in Europe provide valuable insights into the impacts of global warming on lake dynamics, particularly focusing on changes in heat exchange processes to rising temperatures.

The study on Lake Constance investigated the causes of increasing water temperatures in the lake between 1984 and 2011. By analysing heat flux contributions to the overall heat balance, the researchers found that the warming of the lake surface was primarily driven by increases in solar and longwave radiation absorption. The enhanced absorption rates of solar and longwave radiation led to noticeable temperature increases in the lake. Additionally, latent heat flux and longwave emission also increased as a consequence of rising lake surface temperatures. Despite these modifications, the lake's total heat budget remained relatively constant, with heat fluxes balancing out as the water temperature rose. *The study highlighted that the contribution of inflowing rivers to the lake's heat content change had not significantly altered, indicating a negligible cooling effect.* This research underscores the importance of understanding heat exchange dynamics in lake ecosystems to comprehend variations in lake temperature accurately (Fink et al., 2014).

2.1.3. Climate and Mesoscale Meteorology

The studies on the impact of lakes on numerical weather prediction and climate modelling provide valuable insights into the role of lakes in influencing mesoscale meteorology and global climate dynamics. By integrating lake models into forecasting systems and

evaluating their performance across different regions and climates, researchers have shed light on the complex interactions between lakes, surface energy balance, and atmospheric processes.

A study focused on incorporating the Fresh shallow-water Lake model (FLake) into the ECMWF Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) to couple resolved and sub grid lakes with the atmospheric model. By initializing lake variables such as surface water temperature and freezing conditions, the researchers conducted forecast experiments to assess the impact of lakes on near-surface temperature predictions. The results indicated that the inclusion of sub grid lakes led to improved forecast accuracy, particularly in Northern Canada and Scandinavia, attributed to the thermal influence of lakes moderating temperature responses to seasonal radiation forcing. This study underscores the importance of accurately representing lake processes in numerical weather prediction models to enhance forecast skill, especially in regions where lakes play a significant role in local climate dynamics (Balsamo et al., 2012).

In another study, the FLake Lake model was integrated into the ECMWF land-surface scheme, HTESSEL, for global offline simulations to evaluate its performance and influence on the surface energy balance. Using ECMWF reanalysis data, the researchers assessed the model's sensitivity to variations in lake depth and the impact of snow insulation on lake ice cover duration. The findings revealed changes in surface energy storage distribution and energy flux partitioning, particularly in high-latitude and equatorial regions. By

incorporating lake models into General Circulation Models, this study highlights the potential for improving weather forecasting and climate modelling by capturing the feedback between lakes, land surface processes, and atmospheric dynamics (Dutra et al., 2010).

Furthermore, studies utilizing historical satellite data to analyse long-term trends in Lake Surface Water Temperature (LSWT) have provided valuable insights into regional warming patterns and seasonal variations in lake temperatures. The development of continuous time series data for LSWT, validated against in-situ measurements, has enabled the assessment of temperature trends in lakes with limited observational data. These studies have revealed significant warming trends in lake surface temperatures, emphasizing the importance of monitoring LSWT as an essential climate variable for understanding climate change impacts on freshwater ecosystems (Pareeth et al., 2017).

The global synthesis study on lake surface water temperatures highlighted a rapid increase in summer temperatures across lakes worldwide, challenging the notion of regional consistency in warming trends. The research identified complex drivers of lake warming, including rising air temperatures, solar radiation, and changes in cloud cover, leading to non-uniform trends in surface water temperatures. These findings underscore the urgency of addressing climate change impacts on lakes and freshwater ecosystems, emphasizing the need for adaptive strategies to mitigate the consequences of warming lakes on ecosystem health and water quality (O'Reilly et al., 2015).

In conclusion, the collective findings from the studies discussed underscore the critical importance of understanding the intricate and multifaceted impacts of temperature variations on aquatic ecosystems and lake dynamics. These studies highlight the significant influence of rising temperatures on trophic dynamics, nutrient cycling, primary production, algal concentrations, and overall ecosystem functioning in lakes and freshwater environments. By showing the complex interplay between temperature changes, heat exchange processes, water quality alterations, and ecosystem responses, researchers emphasize the urgent need for proactive measures to mitigate the adverse effects of global warming on aquatic biodiversity and ecosystem integrity.

Moreover, the integration of lake models into weather forecasting systems, the analysis of long-term temperature trends in lakes, and the recognition of Lake Surface Water Temperature (LSWT) as an essential climate variable (Lieberherr & Wunderle, 2018) underscore the pivotal role of lakes in shaping mesoscale meteorology and global climate dynamics. Understanding the interactions between lakes, land surface processes, and atmospheric conditions is crucial for enhancing weather predictions, refining climate projections, and implementing effective ecosystem management strategies in the context of ongoing climate change. These studies collectively emphasize the necessity of comprehensive research and informed decision-making to safeguard the resilience and sustainability of lake ecosystems in the face of environmental challenges.

2.2 LSWT Data Scarcity and Remote Sensing Approach

The scarcity of comprehensive data on lake surface water temperature (LSWT) poses a significant challenge to the study of aquatic ecosystems, climate change impacts, and environmental management strategies. Traditional methods of measuring water temperature in lakes, such as in-situ thermometers, have limitations that contribute to data scarcity. In-situ measurements, conducted manually or through automatic recording stations, are influenced by the objectives of different organizations, leading to heterogeneous data collection practices. This lack of standardization hinders the creation of consistent and continuous time series of LSWT measurements necessary for in-depth climate change studies. The variability in data collection protocols complicates efforts to assess lake dynamics and responses to environmental changes accurately. While in-situ measurements provide valuable insights at specific locations, they lack the spatial coverage required to comprehensively analyse the complex dynamics of lake ecosystems, resulting in a substantial data gap (Zhang et al., 2020).

To address the challenge of data scarcity, innovative approaches leveraging advanced technologies and techniques, including remote sensing and modelling, are being explored to complement in-situ measurements and enhance the spatiotemporal coverage of LSWT data. Remote sensing offers a promising solution to overcome data limitations by providing a broader perspective on lake surface temperatures across various lakes, regions, and climatic conditions. By utilizing satellite data and thermal infrared imagery, researchers can

monitor large-scale trends in LSWT and observe significant warming patterns in inland water bodies over extended periods. These remote sensing approaches enable the generation of consistent and reliable LSWT data, essential for understanding the impacts of climate change on aquatic ecosystems and informing evidence-based policy-making and environmental management strategies.

Furthermore, advancements in remote sensing technology have led to the development of novel methodologies for accurately measuring LSWTs over large inland water bodies. By optimizing split-window coefficients tailored to regional atmospheric conditions, researchers have created algorithms like the Inland Water-body Surface Temperature (IWbST) v1.0 algorithm. This innovative approach enhances the accuracy of LSWT measurements derived from satellite sensors, improving the reliability of long-term temperature records for climate studies and monitoring the impact of climate change on inland water bodies worldwide. These remote sensing techniques offer a valuable tool for overcoming data scarcity challenges and advancing the understanding of the dynamic relationship between lake surface temperatures, environmental factors, and climate change impacts (Hulley et al., 2011; Mu et al., 2019).

In conclusion, the integration of remote sensing approaches into the study of LSWT data scarcity represents a crucial step toward addressing the limitations of traditional data collection methods. By leveraging remote sensing technologies and innovative modelling techniques, researchers can enhance the spatial and temporal coverage of LSWT data,

enabling a more comprehensive analysis of lake dynamics, climate change effects, and environmental responses. These advancements in remote sensing offer valuable insights into the complex interactions shaping lake ecosystems and provide essential information for informed decision-making and sustainable environmental management practices.

Up to this point, investigated the potential applications of remote sensing methods to address the challenge of Lake Surface Water Temperature (LSWT) data scarcity. An examination of existing methodologies that are employed to extract LSWT data. These established techniques play a pivotal role in harnessing the power of remote sensing for comprehensive temperature monitoring.

The field of remote sensing offers a lot of tools and methodologies for the retrieval of LSWT, each with its advantages, limitations, and areas of applicability. These methods draw upon the electromagnetic radiation emitted or reflected by the Earth's surface and its water bodies, enabling the estimation of surface water temperatures with varying degrees of accuracy and spatial coverage.

2.3 LSWT derived from Advanced Very High-Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) 1 km data set

This study focused on the development of a satellite-based dataset for Lake Surface Water Temperature (LSWT) in European lakes near the Alps using the Advanced Very High-Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) data record spanning from 1989 to 2013. This dataset aimed to provide accurate and extensive long-term data for climate-related lake studies by

leveraging multiple AVHRR sensors (NOAA and MetOp-A) and employing a simulation-based methodology. The retrieval of LSWT involved meticulous pre-processing steps and considerations for atmospheric conditions to ensure the high accuracy required for climate monitoring. The methodology utilized Radiative Transfer for TOVS (RTTOV) Version 10 and ERA-interim reanalysis data from the European Centre for Medium-range Weather Forecast (Riffler et al., 2015).

The resulting LSWT dataset underwent rigorous validation against in-situ measurements from various-sized lakes, with biases and Root Mean Square Errors (RMSEs) falling within a range of -0.5 to 0.6 K and 1.0 to 1.6 K, respectively. The study suggested that the upper limits of reported errors were more likely due to uncertainties in the data comparison between in-situ and satellite observations rather than inaccuracies in the satellite retrieval process. A comparison with the standard Moderate-resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) Land Surface Temperature product revealed RMSEs and biases within the range of 0.6 to 0.9 and -0.5 to 0.2 K, respectively. The cross-platform consistency of the retrieval was found to be within approximately 0.3 K (Riffler et al., 2015).

The study confirmed that the satellite-derived trend in LSWT was consistent with trends observed from in-situ measurements, indicating that orbital drift did not introduce artificial temperature trends in the dataset. Comparisons with LSWT derived through global sea surface temperature (SST) algorithms showed lower RMSEs and biases for the simulation-based approach. The developed method, as part of an ongoing project, aimed to extend

the retrieval of LSWT for all of Europe, providing valuable insights into the climate signal of the past 30 years. This dataset contributes essential information for monitoring climate-related changes in European lakes, offering a reliable and accurate resource for studying long-term trends in lake surface water temperatures and their implications for climate research and environmental management (Riffler et al., 2015).

2.4 LSWT derived from MODIS LST products

Lake Surface Water Temperature (LSWT) derived from MODIS (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer) Land Surface Temperature (LST) products provides valuable insights into the regional and temporal variations of LSWT, particularly in the context of the Tibetan Plateau (TP). The TP, known as 'the Roof of the World' and 'Asia's water towers,' is a crucial region influencing both regional and global climate dynamics. By compiling a comprehensive dataset spanning 15 years from 2001 to 2015, covering night-time and daytime LSWT for 374 lakes with a minimum area of 10 square kilometres, this study offers a detailed examination of LSWT patterns across the TP region (Wan et al., 2017).

The dataset derived from MODIS LST products and supplemented by Lake Boundary shape files obtained from various satellite images, including Landsat, CBERS, and GaoFen-1, provides a robust foundation for analysing LSWT variations in the TP region. This dataset serves as a valuable resource for a wide range of climate-related applications, including water budget analysis, assessment of lake evaporation rates, monitoring water storage fluctuations, tracking glacier melt, and studying permafrost degradation. By examining the

detailed patterns and variations in LSWT across the TP, researchers can gain a deeper understanding of the impacts of climate change on the region's hydrological cycle, water resources, and environmental dynamics (Wan et al., 2017).

The methods mentioned above, while offering commendable temporal resolution, are deemed unsuitable for monitoring small lakes due to their spatial resolution constraints, primarily limited to 1 km. Consequently, for the research purposes, these methodologies are considered inadequate. Therefore, chosen to utilize Landsat Collection 2 Surface Temperature data, which provides a more suitable spatial resolution for monitoring small lakes. This decision aligns with the specific requirements of the research objectives. It ensures that, effectively analyse and monitor small lake dynamics with the necessary level of detail and precision.

2.5 Landsat Collection 2 Surface Temperature

The U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) has been providing Landsat satellite data since 1972, crucial for historical land surface change studies. To enhance user experience and streamline data utilization, the USGS has undertaken the production of Landsat Level 2 Science Products (L2SP). The latest initiative, Landsat Collection 2 (C2), represents a significant reprocessing effort, incorporating advancements in data processing, algorithm development, and data access and distribution capabilities. This effort aims to improve data product quality and accessibility for more effective and efficient land surface change analyses (Landsat, 2022).

The Landsat 8-9 Surface Temperature (ST) product is based on the single channel algorithm version 1.3.0, originating from the June 2017 release of the RIT ST code. In its Collection 2 iteration, this product is created using Landsat 8-9 Level 1 Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS) band 10. The generation process involves incorporating Top of Atmosphere (TOA) Reflectance, TOA Brightness Temperature (BT), Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer (ASTER) Global Emissivity Dataset (GED) data, ASTER Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) data, and atmospheric profiles obtained from reanalysis data, which include geopotential height, specific humidity, and air temperature (Landsat, 2022).

Figure 2. 1: Landsat 9 Surface Reflectance RGB composite (Bands 4,3,2) (left) and the corresponding colour-enhanced Surface Temperature (right) (Landsat, 2022)

Figure 2.1 provides a contrast between a Landsat 9 Surface Reflectance composite (utilizing Bands 4, 3, and 2) and a colour-enhanced representation of Surface Temperature for a specific region in Nepal. The imagery is derived from Landsat 9 data acquired on January 19, 2022 (Path 141, Row 40). Cooler temperatures are represented by blue areas in the

Surface Temperature product, while warmer temperatures are indicated by red areas (Landsat, 2022).

2.5.1. Known issues

The Landsat 8-9 Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS) data, specifically LT08/LT09, poses limitations in processing to Top of Atmosphere (TOA) Brightness Temperature or Surface Temperature. The Surface Temperature (ST) algorithm relies on the Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer Global Emissivity Dataset (ASTER GED) from the Land Processes Distributed Active Archive Centre (LP DAAC). In cases where ASTER GED data is unavailable, corresponding gaps are present in the Landsat ST product. Successful processing of Surface Temperature requires data products with both sunlit optical and thermal data, such as LC08 products for Landsat 8 and LC09 products for Landsat 9. This integration is crucial for obtaining accurate Surface Temperature, utilizing Landsat NDVI and Normalized Difference Snow Index (NDSI) for temporal adjustments to the ASTER GED product. It is noteworthy that night-time acquisitions cannot undergo processing to Surface Temperature. Additionally, a recognized error exists in Landsat Surface Temperature retrievals concerning clouds and potential cloud shadows. Figure 2.2 illustrates the map depicting the coverage of ASTER GED emissivity tiles for the study area (Landsat, 2022).

Figure 2. 2: ASTER Global Emissivity Dataset 100-meter HDF5 V003 for Study Area, footprint (Right) Corresponding colour enhanced Emissivity Dataset (Left)

2.5.2. Evaluation of Landsat surface temperature product

Surface skin temperature is subject to rapid spatial and temporal variations influenced by various environmental factors. To accurately derive temperature data from satellite thermal infrared (TIR) radiance, corrections for atmospheric absorption and temperature effects and knowledge or retrieval of the spectral surface emissivity are essential. The Landsat series, including Landsat 4, 5, 7, 8, and 9, have played crucial roles in capturing TIR data. Landsat 4 and 5 TM featured a single 120-m TIR band centred at approximately 11.4 μm , while Landsat 7 ETM+ introduced a 60-m TIR band with low and high gain settings. Landsat 8 and 9, equipped with the Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS), offer two 100-m bands centred at 10.8 μm and 12.0 μm . However, earlier Landsat missions, such as Landsat 1–3, lacked TIR spectral bands, with Landsat 3 experiencing a failure shortly after launch (Crawford et al., 2023).

The Landsat 8 Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS) offers two bands, allowing for improved surface temperature estimation through a split window algorithm, which minimizes the effects of atmospheric absorption. However, post-launch issues were identified with the Landsat 8 TIRS bands, particularly the 12.0 μm band, related to stray light. To address this, compensation was applied using an optical stray light model, primarily at the swath edges. Corrected TIRS data subsequently demonstrated the capability to retrieve surface temperatures with a mean error of 0.2 K. Despite this advancement, Collection 2 Level 2 surface temperature products utilize a single channel algorithm due to scheduling constraints, with Landsat 7 ETM+ surface temperature derived from both low and high gain 11.4 μm radiance for improved pixel retrievals (Crawford et al., 2023).

The Collection 2 Level 2 Surface Temperature product offers global coverage for daytime images (solar zenith $<76^\circ$) captured by Landsat 4–9. Surface temperature data, provided on a 30 m grid, are consistent with shortwave datasets, despite the nominal resolution of the Thermal Infrared (TIR) data being coarser (60–120 m). Each pixel includes information about the uncertainty of surface temperature measurement in Kelvin, facilitating downstream analysis of retrieval quality (Table 2.1). Additionally, the product includes data on atmospheric transmittance, upwelled path radiance, and down welled sky radiance, enhancing traceability in product generation. The algorithm behind the Collection 2 surface temperature product is based on the MODerate resolution atmospheric TRANsmission (MODTRAN) radiative transfer code. The MODTRAN algorithm utilizes contemporaneous atmospheric auxiliary information (Table 2.2), such as air temperature, geopotential height,

and specific humidity profiles, extracted from either Modern-Era Retrospective analysis for Research and Application, Version 2 (MERRA-2) or Goddard Earth Observing System-5 (GEOS-5) Forward Processing for Instrument Teams (FP-IT) reanalysis data, depending on the image acquisition date. To derive surface temperature, spectral emissivity at 11.3 μm (for Landsat 4–7) and 10.7 μm (for Landsat 8–9) is required, which is obtained from the Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer (ASTER) Global Emissivity Database (GEDv3). This database provides near-global coverage of spectral emissivity values derived from ASTER TIR bands using the Temperature Emissivity Separation (TES) algorithm. The mean spectral emissivity associated with Landsat TIR bands is estimated by applying sensor-specific regression coefficients on ASTER 10.7 and 11.3 μm bands. As the ASTER GEDv3 is static, adjustments are made to account for vegetation and snow cover changes during Landsat overpass conditions (Crawford et al., 2023).

Table 2. 1: Landsat Collection 2 Level 1 and Level 2 per-pixel quality assessment (QA)
(Crawford et al., 2023)

QA Band	Description
Landsat 4–9 Pixel Quality Assessment (QA_PIXEL)	<p>Derived from the Function of Mask (FMask) version 3.3.1, the bit-packed Pixel QA defines certain quality conditions such as</p> <p>Cloud, cloud shadow, and snow/ice flags with associated confidence levels. The cirrus and cirrus confidence levels in</p> <p>Landsat 8–9 QA_PIXEL is determined using a separate cirrus detection algorithm. A water flag is also included to support</p> <p>Advanced-level science products. The high-confidence cloud pixels are dilated (3- pixels) and flagged as such in this QA band</p>
Landsat 4–9 Radiometric Saturation QA (QA_RADSAT)	<p>Represents which sensor bands were saturated during data capture, yielding unusable data. Saturation is not common in</p> <p>Landsat 8/9. Saturation occurs over the reflective surfaces in the Visible and Near Infrared (VNIR) bands, or volcanoes and</p> <p>wildfires in the Shortwave Infrared (SWIR) and thermal bands.</p>
Landsat 8/9 Aerosol QA (SR_QA_AEROSOL)	<p>An internal Landsat 8/9 Land Surface Reflectance Code (LaSRC) QA band provides low-level details about the validity of the aerosol retrieval. It also shows whether a terrestrial or water-based routine was used for aerosol determination. The Aerosol QA also indicates if the aerosol</p> <p>was inverted or interpolated from the centre of 3 × 3 windows.</p>
Landsat 4–9 ST Uncertainty (ST_QA)	<p>Provides the per-pixel ST product uncertainty (K). The uncertainty propagation model includes the uncertainty in atmospheric variables, Landsat radiance uncertainty, the error associated with the Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer (ASTER) Global Emissivity Dataset (GED) emissivity, and uncertainties in the distance to cloud and transmission.</p>

Table 2. 2: Atmospheric auxiliary data ingest for Landsat Collection 2 Level 2 product generation. (Crawford et al., 2023)

Level 2 Product	Algorithm	USGS Algorithm Ver.	Radiative Transfer Model/ Program	Auxiliary data	Description	Horizontal Resolution	Latency
Surface Temperature	Single Channel	1.3.0	MODTRAN	NOAA ETOPOS DEM	Digital Elevation Model	5 arcmin	Static
				MERRA-2 (1982–12/31/1999),	Atmosphere profiles of geopotential	0.625 × 0.5 deg	18 h
				GEOS FP-IT (01/01/2000-present); transition to GEOS IT is underway.	height, specific humidity, and air temperature		
				ASTER GED	Surface emissivity	100 m	Static
GLS DEM, NASADEM, CDEM, SNF, Alaska NED, GIMP, NPI, ArcticDEM	Regional digital elevation model	3 arcsec	Static				

The Collection 2 Landsat surface temperature product underwent validation using Landsat 5 and 7 data across land, inland water, and coastal water sites, achieving an accuracy within 0.51 K and precision of 1.56 K. Validation of the Collection 2 Landsat 8 surface temperature product encompassed various land sites, demonstrating an accuracy of approximately 0.5 K and precision of around 1 K, with notably better performance over lake and coastal water sites (Figure 2.3). However, validation across diverse geographic regions and land surface types, including Landsat 4–9, is still required for comprehensive assessment of the Collection 2 surface temperature products (Crawford et al., 2023).

Figure 2. 3: Example validation of the Collection 2 Landsat 8 surface temperature products for land sites (left) and lake sites (right) derived from hundreds of cloud-free acquisitions acquired 2018–2021 (Crawford et al., 2023).

2.5.3. Cloud and cloud shadow mask

Cloud and cloud shadow masks are essential components for reliable surface monitoring in remote sensing applications. In Landsat Collection 2, similar to Collection 1, the 30-meter cloud and shadow masks are integrated into both Level 1 and Level 2 products. The per-pixel Quality Assessment (QA) layer in Landsat Collection 2 includes detailed information on the presence of clouds, cloud shadows, cirrus clouds, snow/ice, and water. This QA layer offers varying confidence levels for cloud detection, including low, medium, and high confidence levels, as well as low and high confidence levels for shadow, snow/ice, and cirrus presence (Crawford et al., 2023).

The cloud detection methodology employed in Landsat Collection 2 builds upon a heritage of empirical spectral tests applied to individual image pixels. The algorithm for cloud and cloud shadow masking in Collection 2 is based on the USGS Landsat Collection 1 C Function of Mask (CFMask) algorithm version 3.3.1. Validation studies have shown that the CFMask algorithm achieves an overall accuracy of 90.45%. However, validating cloud mask products can be challenging due to the diverse optical properties and morphologies of clouds. Particularly, detecting clouds over snow and ice, as well as shadows over low reflectance surfaces, presents challenges due to spectral similarities (Crawford et al., 2023).

The Landsat 8 and 9 Operational Land Imager (OLI) instruments include a spectral band at 1.360–1.390 μm , enabling the detection of cirrus clouds with varying levels of confidence. Cirrus cloud detection is crucial due to the prevalence of cirrus clouds in Landsat imagery. The OLI cirrus cloud detection process involves thresholding the Top of Atmosphere (TOA) reflectance in the 1.360–1.390 μm range, with adjustments made for column water vapour effects based on surface elevation data from the Landsat geolocation Digital Elevation Model (DEM) as outlined in Section 3.1 of the Landsat documentation (Crawford et al., 2023).

Moving forward, improvements in cirrus cloud detection algorithms may be necessary to address potential misclassifications in dry atmospheric conditions and over snow/ice surfaces that exhibit strong reflectance in the 1.360–1.390 μm spectral region.

Enhancements in cirrus detection algorithms will be crucial for ensuring accurate cloud and cloud shadow masking in Landsat Collection 2 data products (Crawford et al., 2023).

Because of temporal challenges associated with the Collection 2 Landsat 8 surface temperature product, characterized by a 16-day acquisition cycle and occasional data unavailability due to cloud cover, made the strategic decision to develop a 1D hydrodynamic model, using the General Lake Model (GLM). This model will enable us to simulate daily variations in lake surface temperature by leveraging the acquired Landsat 2 Collection 2 surface temperature product. By integrating this modelling approach with the satellite-derived data, aim is to address the temporal limitations of the Landsat product and enhance the ability to analyse and predict daily fluctuations in lake surface temperature with improved accuracy and temporal resolution.

2.6 GLM overview

The General Lake Model (GLM) is an open-source, one-dimensional software developed specifically to simulate the hydrodynamics of lakes, reservoirs, and wetlands. Its creation was motivated by the research requirements of the Global Lake Ecological Observatory Network (GLEON), an international collaboration of scientists utilizing sensor technology to study lake dynamics. GLM serves as a valuable tool for investigating how lakes globally are influenced by climate variations and changes in land use (Hipsey et al., 2019).

The GLM model integrates user-provided meteorological surface data and inflow/outflow information to simulate the water balance and energy dynamics of lakes. It employs a

Lagrangian layer structure similar to other one-dimensional models to compute vertical profiles of temperature, density, and salinity. This design allows layers to adjust their thickness in response to various factors such as inflows/outflows, mixing, and surface mass fluxes. The number and thickness of layers are determined by user-defined parameters. Over time, layers can merge or split based on the available energy from surface forcing and inflows, simulating mixing and density stratification processes. Water quality properties remain uniform within each layer, resulting in more layers during stratification periods compared to isothermal conditions (Snorheim, 2015). Despite being a recent addition to modelling frameworks, GLM's foundation lies in established principles and expertise drawn from pre-existing model platforms such as the Dynamic Reservoir Simulation Model (DYRESM) (Hipsey et al., 2019).

2.6.1. Layer Structure

In the GLM, the determination of lake volume (V_{\max}) relies on the site-specific hypsographic curve, defined as the integral of the area (A) for elevation (H). Mathematically, this can be expressed as:

$$V_{\max} = \int_{H_0}^{H_{\max}} A[H] dH \quad (1)$$

The hypsographic curve is constructed from bathymetric data, requiring the user to provide a set of elevations and their corresponding areas. The cumulative volume at any elevation (V_b) is computed iteratively based on neighbouring elevation-area pairs, with adjustments made to account for changes in elevation and area along the curve. This adjustment is determined by the following equation:

$$V_b = V_{b-1} + 0.5 \times (A_b + A_{b-1}) \times (H_b - H_{b-1}) \quad (2)$$

where ($2 \leq b \leq N_{\text{BSN}}$) Using these raw hypsographic data, a refined height–area–volume relationship is then internally computed using finer height increments, giving (N_{MORPH}) levels that are used for subsequent calculations. The area and volume at the height of each increment, (H_{mi}), are interpolated from the supplied information as:

$$V_{mi} = V_b \times \left(\frac{H_{mi}}{H_b}\right)^{\alpha_b} \quad \text{and} \quad A_{mi} = A_b \times \left(\frac{H_{mi}}{H_b}\right)^{\beta_b} \quad (3)$$

where (V_{mi}) and (A_{mi}) are the volume and area at each of the elevations of the interpolated depth vector, (H_{mi}). (V_b) and (A_b) refer to the nearest b level below (H_{mi}) such that ($H_b < H_{mi}$). The interpolation coefficients are computed as:

$$\alpha_b = \frac{\log_{10}\left(\frac{V_{b+1}}{V_b}\right)}{\log_{10}\left(\frac{H_{b+1}}{H_b}\right)} \quad \text{and} \quad \beta_b = \frac{\log_{10}\left(\frac{A_{b+1}}{A_b}\right)}{\log_{10}\left(\frac{H_{b+1}}{H_b}\right)} \quad (4)$$

The GLM manages the water balance through user-configurable water fluxes, which influence the layer structure of the lake. These fluxes include surface mass fluxes (e.g., evaporation, rainfall, and snowfall), inflows (e.g., surface and submerged inflows, local runoff), and outflows (e.g., withdrawals, overflow, seepage). The dynamics of these fluxes alter the overall lake water balance and layer structure on both sub-daily and daily time steps.

Each layer in the GLM contains heat, salt, and other constituents, collectively referred to as scalars, which are subject to mass conservation principles. Density computations within layers are based on local salinity and temperature according to TEOS-10 standards. Density instabilities trigger merging of adjacent layers, facilitating mixing processes, particularly in response to changes in solar radiation and thermocline formation.

Numerical diffusion at the thermocline can be minimized by adjusting the layer structure and mixing algorithm parameters, making the GLM suitable for long-term investigations with minimal site-specific calibration requirements. This versatility allows researchers and practitioners to apply the GLM across various aquatic systems, facilitating comprehensive assessments of hydrological processes and ecosystem dynamics (Hipsey et al., 2019).

2.6.2. Water balance

The model's adaptability to various lake types requires flexible configurations for water inputs and outputs, as depicted in Figure 2.4. The net water flux across the entire lake is represented by the equation:

$$\frac{dV_S}{dt} = A \frac{dh_S}{dt} + \sum_I^{N_{INF}} Q_{info_I} - \sum_O^{N_{OUTF}} Q_{outf_O} - (Q_{seepage} + Q_{ovfl}) \quad (5)$$

where (V_S) is the total lake volume, (t) represents time, and (A_S) is the lake surface area. This equation accounts for changes in water volume due to fluxes at the water surface (h_S), with further explanations provided below. For practical implementation, the equation is numerically solved in two stages with different time steps for surface flux changes and all other fluxes. Additionally, not all inputs and outputs may be relevant for a particular application, allowing users to customize the water balance components accordingly.

The surface layer's mass balance is computed at each time step (Δt), typically hourly) by adjusting the surface layer height (h_S) according to:

$$\frac{dh_S}{dt} = R_F + S_F + \frac{Q_R}{A_S} - E - \frac{d\Delta z_{ice}}{dt} \quad (6)$$

Where (E) represents the evaporation mass flux, (R_F) is rainfall, (S_F) is snowfall, (Q_R) accounts for runoff, and (Δz_{ice}) denotes ice layer changes. The equations for (R_F) and (S_F) are adjusted based on meteorological conditions and ice cover presence. Additionally, (Q_R) considers runoff to the lake from riparian banks, computed using a simple model based on rainfall intensity and a runoff coefficient (Hipsey et al., 2019).

Figure 2. 4: Schematic of a GLM simulation domain, input information (blue text) and key simulated processes (black text) (Hipsey et al., 2019).

2.6.3. Surface energy balance

The equilibrium between shortwave and longwave radiation fluxes, along with sensible and evaporative heat fluxes, governs the net heating or cooling of the lake surface. The heat budget equation for the topmost layer is represented as:

$$c_w \cdot \rho_s \cdot Z_s \cdot \frac{dT_s}{dt} = \Phi_{SWS} - \Phi_E + \Phi_H + \Phi_{LW_{in}} + \Phi_{LW_{out}} \quad (7)$$

Here, (c_w) denotes the specific heat capacity of water, (T_s) signifies the surface temperature, while (Z_s) and (ρ_s) correspond to the depth and density of the surface layer

(where $(i = N_{LEV})$), respectively. The terms on the right-hand side (RHS) are computed numerically during each time step and offer various options for customizing individual surface heat flux components. (Φ_{SWS}) , represents the shortwave radiation flux that contributes to heating the surface mixed layer. This flux is quantified in Wm^{-2} and is computed based on user-provided solar radiation data, along with other options configured within the model. $(\Phi_{LW_{in}})$, which denotes the incident longwave radiation heat flux at the water surface. If the net or incoming longwave flux is not explicitly provided, the model has the capability to compute this flux autonomously, ensuring the inclusion of this critical component in the energy balance calculations. $(\Phi_{LW_{out}})$ signifies the outgoing longwave radiation heat flux from the water surface. This flux is also determined within the model, ensuring a comprehensive consideration of radiative heat transfer processes. In addition to radiative fluxes, the model addresses the surface fluxes of sensible heat (Φ_H) and latent heat (Φ_E) . These fluxes are managed using commonly adopted bulk aerodynamic formulae, allowing for the incorporation of atmospheric influences on heat exchange at the water surface (Hipsey et al., 2019).

In the (Hipsey et al., 2019) paper, a comprehensive description of the General Lake Model (GLM) unfolds, offering readers a detailed insight into its functionality and applicability. The explanation navigates various critical domains, explaining the model's treatment of solar heating and light penetration phenomena, the dynamics of longwave radiation, and the details of sensible and latent heat transfer mechanisms. Furthermore, the paper delves into the GLM's capacity to address non-neutral atmospheric stability issues, considerations for

wind sheltering effects, and the description of still-air limits, providing a holistic perspective on the model's adaptability. Within this discourse, the nuanced dynamics of snow and ice, alongside the thermal dynamics of sediment heating, are precisely explored. The narrative extends to clarify the model's treatment of stratification and vertical mixing processes, shedding light on how these phenomena are integrated into the broader framework. Additionally, the paper outlines the GLM's approach to simulating inflows and outflows within the lake environment, offering insights into its comprehensive modelling capabilities. With this detailed exposition, readers gain a comprehensive understanding of the GLM's robust framework and its ability to simulate complex lake dynamics across diverse environmental contexts. This comprehensive overview serves as a solid foundation for further exploration and application of the GLM in various research and management endeavours.

2.7 GLM on LSWT

In this study conducted by (Zhang et al., 2020), the primary focus was on conducting a direct comparison between skin temperature measurements obtained from satellite imagery and bulk temperatures of water column layers derived from observational data. This comparison aimed to explain the relationship between skin temperature and bulk temperature, providing valuable insights into the thermal dynamics of the lake surface. Furthermore, they proposed a novel strategy for adjusting remotely sensed skin temperature to match the bulk temperature of the surface layer. This adjustment

technique served as an efficient bias correction method, enabling the extrapolation of remotely sensed skin temperature observations to produce an alternative data source for their hydrodynamic lake model. One significant scientific contribution of their work lies in the development of a well-calibrated lake model capable of forecasting lake surface temperature with reasonable accuracy using key meteorological variables such as wind speed and solar radiation. This aspect is particularly crucial as it enhances the understanding of how climate change affects shallow and large lakes, especially under eutrophic conditions. For their study, they selected Lake Chaohu, a large shallow lake situated at mid-latitudes in eastern China, as their focal point. Utilizing high-frequency in-situ observations of lake surface water temperature (LSWT), MODIS temperature products, and the General Lake Model (GLM), they generated comparable long-term time series of LSWT.

To achieve objectives, proceeded in several steps: firstly, they evaluated the reliability of MODIS-derived LSWT by comparing it with high-frequency in-situ water temperature observations. Secondly, they assessed the performance of the GLM simulation by comparing in-situ LSWT data with MODIS-derived LSWT at various time scales. Finally, they utilized these methodologies to reproduce LSWT observations over 57 years, enabling them to quantify the climatic variability of LSWT and its response to changing environmental conditions. This comprehensive approach allowed them to gain valuable insights into the thermal dynamics of Lake Chaohu and provided a robust framework for

understanding how climatic factors influence its surface temperature over long temporal scales (Zhang et al., 2020).

In Lake Chaohu, in situ temperature data was collected using loggers positioned at six locations across the lake (Figure 2.5), providing insights into the thermal dynamics from January to December 2016, with additional monthly observations available from 2008 to 2016. The data, obtained from depths of 0.3 meters below the surface, allowed for the calculation of daily average temperatures and facilitated the study of temporal variations in water temperature within the lake (Zhang et al., 2020).

Figure 2. 5: Location of Lake Chaohu at the Anhui Province in China, sampling sites for water temperature (Zhang et al., 2020).

This study employed Moderate-Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) data to derive daily Lake Surface Water Temperature (LSWT), utilizing both Terra and Aqua overpasses for comprehensive coverage. To pre-process the data, the split-window algorithm was applied and removed cloud-contaminated temperatures, ensuring accurate retrievals. LSWT data from MOD11A1 and MYD11A1 products spanning from 2002 to 2016 were utilized, providing extensive temporal coverage for the analysis (Zhang et al., 2020).

Comparisons between MODIS-derived LSWT and in situ observations were conducted at both site-specific and whole-lake scales. At the site level, real-time comparisons were made between MODIS-derived LSWT and in situ measurements obtained from six locations across Lake Chaohu. The extracted 3x3 pixel matrix centred on sample sites facilitated representative temperature estimation from MODIS images. Daily LSWT values over the entire lake area were then computed and averaged, with outliers removed to ensure data reliability (Zhang et al., 2020).

Post-processing involved addressing issues such as cloud contamination and systematic biases in MODIS-derived LSWT. An Upper Envelop smoothing method was employed to minimize differences and obtain a reliable daily time series of LSWT, effectively reducing negative noise and enhancing data quality.

$$LST_{u-e}(t) = \max \left[LST(t), \left(0.5 \cdot LST(t) + 0.25 \cdot (LST(t-1) + LST(t+1)) \right) \right] \quad (8)$$

The equation represents the computation of MODIS temperature using the Upper Envelop method, denoted as $(LST_{u-e}(t))$. It is derived from the maximum value between the current MODIS temperature $(LST(t))$ and a weighted average of the temperature at the current time step and its neighboring time steps. Specifically, $(LST(t), LST(t - 1))$, and $(LST(t + 1))$ represent the temperatures at the time (t) , of the previous time step, and the following time step, respectively (Zhang et al., 2020).

Quantitative evaluation metrics including bias, standard error (STD), and root mean square error (RMSE) were employed to assess the quality and accuracy of LSWT estimates from different data sources. Linear trend analysis and Pearson correlation coefficients were utilized to analyse LSWT and related atmospheric variables, providing insights into long-term trends and relationships. Additionally, change-point tests of the LSWT time series were conducted using sequential t-tests and the CUSUM (the cumulative sum) method combined with bootstrap analysis, enabling the detection of significant shifts in temperature trends over time. This comprehensive approach facilitated a thorough evaluation of MODIS-derived LSWT data and its utility in understanding lake dynamics and climate influences (Zhang et al., 2020).

The GLM model (v2.4.0) utilized various meteorological variables including wind speed, air temperature, relative humidity, precipitation, shortwave radiation, and longwave radiation as input data. These variables were obtained from the Hefei weather station dataset provided by the China Meteorological Administration from 1960 to 2016. The model

calibration involved minimizing the RMSE by comparing simulated data with observed MODIS-derived LSWT and in situ data from 2016. Additionally, shortwave radiation was calculated from observed sunshine duration. The GLM also estimated incoming longwave radiation. During the model simulation, heat effects from inflows and outflows were neglected due to their minimal impact on water temperature, as observed in previous studies. Default parameter values were used for most settings, except for the light extinction coefficient and wind scaling factor, which were calibrated to minimize RMSE. The GLM model's performance was evaluated using statistical criteria such as RMSE, bias, and STD for the period from 2002 to 2016 (Zhang et al., 2020).

The evaluation of the GLM model's performance in simulating Lake Surface Water Temperature (LSWT) yielded promising results. Comparison between LSWT simulations and MODIS-UE LSWT for the year 2016 indicated a small bias and standard deviation of 1.8°C and 1.92°C, respectively, with a high correlation coefficient of 0.98. Excluding summertime data reduced the bias and standard deviation to 1.09°C and 1.53°C, respectively, suggesting that the cool bias observed during summer may have influenced the overall bias. Further validation using monthly-observed LSWT from 2008 to 2016 and MODIS LSWT from 2002 to 2016-revealed good agreement between simulations and observations, with correlations coefficients of 0.96 and 0.94, respectively. Summer values showed slightly lower correlations and biases when excluded. Additionally, the seasonal patterns of simulations aligned well with observed LSWT, particularly during summer, with a bias of -0.03°C and a standard deviation of 1.82°C. The comparison of annual anomaly

values further demonstrated a strong agreement between MODIS–UE LSWT data and GLM simulations, affirming the model's reliability and accuracy for long-term simulations of LSWT changes (Zhang et al., 2020).

In this study, a one-year dataset of detailed Lake Surface Water Temperature (LSWT) measurements was effectively utilized to calibrate the General Lake Model (GLM) using meteorological data from a nearby weather station. The calibrated model demonstrated the ability to simulate LSWT over the entire period for which meteorological data were available. MODIS LSWT data proved valuable for validating the model back to 2002, despite occasional deviations attributed to MODIS cold bias, particularly evident in summer. The numerical simulations offered a means to overcome data gaps inherent in satellite observations, as they were not subject to atmospheric conditions affecting both LSWT and satellite data collection. This approach holds promise for application to other lakes of regional significance (Zhang et al., 2020).

To execute the General Lake Model (GLM), essential meteorological data including rainfall, wind speed, shortwave radiation, cloud cover, and relative humidity daily are imperative. However, the scarcity of such data in the study area poses a significant challenge. As a result, the focus will shift towards exploring the feasibility and applicability of utilizing NASA Power Reanalysis data as an alternative source of meteorological information to support the modelling requirements of the GLM.

2.8 NASA Power

Weather variables play a crucial role in decision-making processes worldwide. However, in many regions, the lack of observational data or poor data quality poses significant challenges. To address this, reanalysis and gridding meteorological data from global atmospheric models have emerged as valuable sources to compensate for these deficiencies. Reanalysis involves the comprehensive analysis of observations, incorporating improved quality control measures and assimilating models to enhance data homogeneity and usefulness for studying weather variations (Rodrigues & Braga, 2021).

Various historical reanalysis datasets are available, including the Climate Forecast System Reanalysis (CFSR), ERA-Interim, JRA-55, NCEP/NCAR, MERRA, and NASA POWER. Among these, NASA POWER offers a user-friendly interface and provides daily data on near-surface air temperature, relative humidity, rainfall, solar radiation, and wind speed and direction. This study has a dataset derived from simulations of numerical weather prediction models based on meteorological observations (Rodrigues & Braga, 2021).

In a study conducted in the Alentejo region of Southern Portugal, daily meteorological NASA POWER reanalysis data was compared with observations from 14 local weather stations. The objectives were to assess the accuracy of NASA POWER data and to evaluate alternative bias correction procedures to improve reanalysis accuracy. This research demonstrates the potential of reanalysis data, such as NASA POWER, in providing reliable

weather information, particularly in regions with limited observational data or data quality issues (Rodrigues & Braga, 2021).

Two bias correction schemes were applied: regional and local bias correction. The correction involved shifting and scaling to adjust the mean and variance. Validation was conducted using independent datasets to ensure the accuracy of the correction procedure. Results showed improvements in accuracy metrics for maximum temperature, minimum temperature, solar radiation, relative humidity, and wind speed after bias correction. Notably, solar radiation estimation by NASA POWER exhibited excellent accuracy even without bias correction. The findings suggest the potential of bias correction methods to enhance the accuracy of reanalysis data, particularly for applications in agriculture and environmental studies (Rodrigues & Braga, 2021).

3. CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study Area

Lake Gregory (Figure 3.1), situated in the uppermost hill capital of Nuwara Eliya in Sri Lanka, is a man-made water body with a rich history dating back to its construction in 1874 by the British Governor at that time. Located at 06°53'.816N and 080°52'.536E, and an elevation of 1800 meters above Mean Sea Level, this lake holds historically and environmentally significant importance (Shirantha et al., 2010).

Initially created by damming the Thalagala Oya, which is a prominent upper stream of the Nanu Oya that eventually flows into the Kotmale Oya, a tributary of the River Mahaweli, Lake Gregory served the purpose of feeding a mini-hydropower plant at the Black Pool area. However, with the closure of the hydro-power plant, the focus shifted towards enhancing the aesthetic beauty of the surroundings and utilizing the lake as a sport fishing ground (Shirantha et al., 2010).

Covering an area of 40 hectares, Lake Gregory's catchment area comprises several natural streams originating from the Piduruthalagala mountain range in the north-western region, the Kandapola area in the north-eastern region, and the Magastota area in the south-eastern region. Additionally, the lake receives water from various inflow culverts from the Nuwara Eliya municipal area (Shirantha et al., 2010).

The lake is fed by these natural streams and connects to the Nanu Oya from the southwestern side. The Nanu Oya, in turn, intersects with several other perennial streams that flow through natural forest areas and plantations, enriching the lake's water sources and contributing to its ecological diversity (Shirantha et al., 2010).

Lake Gregory's surroundings are not only attractive but also ecologically significant, with the diverse inflow of water from different sources creating a unique habitat for various flora and fauna. The lake's transformation from a power generation site to a recreational and scenic spot underscores its adaptive reuse and the importance of balancing human needs with environmental conservation (Shirantha et al., 2010).

Figure 3. 1: Lake Gregory

3.2 Research Methodology

The methodology as shown in Figure 3.2 involved multiple stages of data acquisition, processing, model development, calibration, and analysis. Lake surface temperature data were obtained from the Landsat Level 2 Collection 2 Surface Temperature product and processed using ArcMap 10.8. Meteorological data for the lake region were sourced from NASA Power Reanalysis and compared with observed data to ensure compatibility for use as input for the General Lake Model (GLM).

The GLM was developed to simulate lake surface temperature. Sensitive parameters were identified through an iterative process, and the model was calibrated and validated against Landsat surface temperatures and observed data provided by the Department of Irrigation (ANNEX 05). Once validated, the model was applied to analyse the impacts of various climatic scenarios.

Figure 3. 2: Research Methodology

3.3 Acquisition and Processing of Bathymetry Data for Lake Gregory Using Historical Surveys

To obtain bathymetry data for Lake Gregory, a survey conducted by the Sri Lanka Land Development Corporation in 1988 was utilized as a primary data source. The survey records, available in scanned PDF file format (Figure 3.3), contained valuable information regarding the underwater topography of Lake Gregory. To transform this historical survey data into a comprehensive bathymetric map, a careful approach involving the scaling of

drawings and integration within a Geographic Information System (GIS) software, QGIS was undertaken.

The process of scaling the scanned drawings from the 1988 survey involved accurately resizing the digital images to match real-world dimensions. By calibrating the scanned drawings with known reference points, the bathymetric features of Lake Gregory were effectively translated into a digital format suitable for further analysis and mapping.

Then, the scaled drawings from the historical survey were integrated and merged within the QGIS platform to develop a detailed bathymetry map of Lake Gregory (Figure 3.4). Enabling the creation of a comprehensive representation of the lake's underwater topography.

Figure 3. 3: Survey conducted by the Sri Lanka Land Development Corporation in 1988

Figure 3. 4: develop a detailed bathymetry map of Lake Gregory

3.4 Landsat Collection 2 surface temperature data processing

3.4.1. Data Downloaded process

In the study conducted to process Landsat Collection 2 surface temperature data, the initial step involved locating the data for the years 2017 to 2018 using a map polygon in the USGS Earth Explorer platform. The selected time frame for the data extraction was set from the 1st of January 2017 to the 31st of December 2021. (Figure 3.5)

Figure 3. 5: Search criteria in USGS earth explore

In the data set tab, the Landsat 8-9 Operational Land Imager (OLI) and Thermal Infrared (TIRS) Collection 2 Level-2 Science Products 30-meter multispectral data were selected for analysis. As shown in Figure 3.6

Figure 3. 6: Data Set

The study area was geospatially identified to be situated within the WRS path 141 and WRS row 055, surrounding the entirety of a lake within the designated Landsat tile. This specific location falls within the framework of the Worldwide Reference System (WRS) utilized by the Landsat program for systematic cataloguing and referencing of satellite imagery. A visual inspection process was undertaken to overlay each tile containing the study area. This visual examination aimed to identify and isolate clear images devoid of significant cloud cover interference. Images exhibiting heavy cloud cover, which could potentially obscure or distort the surface temperature, were systematically excluded from further analysis. As shown in Figure 3.7 and Figure 3.8.

Figure 3. 7: Clear sky image over Lake Gregory Dated 2021.12.26

Figure 3. 8: Cloud Covered Image Over Lake Gregory Dated 2021.10.23

After utilizing the USGS bulk downloader tool, initially accessed the JAVA version for downloading data. However, as of the 17th of August 2022, the JAVA version has been discontinued, and the tool is now exclusively accessible as a web application. In this context, proceeded to download specific Landsat Collection 2 Level-2 band files, namely QA_PIXEL.TIF, ST_B10.TIF, and ST_QA.TIF, using the Java application for data retrieval.

The file name structure comprises the Landsat Product ID as the initial segment, followed by the file type and extension components detailed in the respective Table 3.1. The combination of the Landsat Product ID, file type, and extension forms the complete file name format, incorporating specific identifiers and descriptors for each file (Landsat, 2022).

LXSS_LLLL_PPPRRR_YYYYMMDD_yyyymmdd_CC_TX_FT.ext

Table 3. 1: Landsat Product Identifier (Landsat, 2022)

Identifier	Description
L	Landsat
X	Sensor of: C = Combined TIRS and OLI Indicates which sensor collected data for this product
SS	Landsat satellite (08 for Landsat 8, 09 for Landsat 9)
LLLL	Processing level (L2SP, L2SR)
PPP	Satellite orbit location about the Worldwide Reference System-2 (WRS-2) path of the product
RRR	Satellite orbit location in reference to the WRS-2 row of the product
YYYY	Acquisition year of the image
MM	Acquisition month of the image
DD	Acquisition day of the image
YYYY	Processing year of the image
mm	Processing month of the image
dd	Processing day of the image
CC	Collection number (e.g., 02)
TX	Collection category: "T1" for Tier 1 (highest quality), "T2" for Tier 2
FT	File type, where FT equals one of the following: MTL (metadata file), MD5 (checksum file), (SR_B1-7) (Surface Reflectance Bands), (ST_B10) (Surface Temperature Band), SR_QA_AEROSOL (Aerosol retrieval per pixel), QA_PIXEL (Level-1 QA Band), QA_RADSAT (Radiometric saturation per pixel), ST_QA (Surface Temperature QA), ST_TRAD (Thermal band converted to radiance), ST_URAD (Upwelled Radiance), ST_DRAD (Downwelled Radiance), ST_ATRAN (Atmospheric Transmittance), ST_EMIS (Emissivity estimated from ASTER GED Band 10), ST_EMSD (Emissivity

	standard deviation), ST_CDIST (Pixel distance to cloud), ANG (angle coefficient file)
ext	File extension, where. TIF equals COG file extension, .xml equals XML extension (metadata), and .txt equals text extension

3.4.2. The delineated water body of Lake Gregory

In the effort to extract Lake Gregory from Landsat satellite imagery, a systematic methodology was employed. Initially, a cloud-free day was selected for observation over the lake, specifically on the 22nd of April 2022. Subsequently, Landsat tiles corresponding to this date were chosen to capture the desired spectral bands for analysis. The bands of interest, namely Band 5 (Near-Infrared), Band 6 (Shortwave Infrared 1), and Band 4 (Red), were composited using advanced raster composite band tools to create a comprehensive multispectral image (refer to Figure 3.9).

Figure 3. 9: Produced tile after using Composite band tool

Following the composite image, an unsupervised cluster classification approach was implemented using the composited bands. This classification technique, with a predetermined number of classes set at 6, aimed to segment the image into distinct clusters based on spectral similarities, thereby facilitating the identification of different land cover types within the scene (see Figure 3.10).

Figure 3. 10: unsupervised cluster classification

After the cluster classification process, a reclassification procedure was conducted to isolate pixels corresponding to Lake Gregory from the rest of the classified categories. By delineating lake pixels and categorizing them separately from the other five classes, a refined classification output was achieved, enhancing the specificity of the analysis (refer to Figure 3.11).

Figure 3. 11: Reclassified image

The extract by mask tool was utilized to isolate a specific area surrounding the lake (see Figure 3.12)

Figure 3. 12: Extracted surrounding area of Lake Gregory

The extracted area containing Lake Gregory was subjected to further refinement using the extract by attributes tool, which facilitated the separation of the lake area from the surrounding land cover class. This step ensured the accurate delineation and extraction of Lake Gregory from the Landsat imagery (refer to Figure 3.13).

Figure 3. 13: Extracted Raster of Lake Gregory

Finally, the raster data containing the extracted Lake Gregory area was converted into a vector shape file format for further application in extracting surface temperatures and quality bands from Landsat images (see Figure 3.14).

Figure 3. 14: Extracted shape file of Lake Gregory

3.4.3. Surface temperature data extraction process in ArcMap

In the process of converting Landsat surface temperature data from the ProductID_ST_B10 band to Kelvin units, a careful approach involving scaling factors was implemented as per the guidelines in (Landsat, 2022). The scaling factors, comprising a Multiplicative Scale Factor of 0.00341802 and an Additive Offset of 149, were applied to the ST_B10 band data to facilitate the conversion to Kelvin. To execute this conversion process efficiently across multiple images, the ArcMap model builder was utilized as a comprehensive geospatial tool. The model builder workflow, as depicted in Figure 3.15, commenced with the "Iterate Raster" function, which served to extract the ST_B10 tiles from the "Landsat C2 Band Files" directory where the data was stored. This iterative process enabled the systematic retrieval of each ST_B10 tile for subsequent processing within the model builder framework.

Then, each ST_B10 raster file is transformed using the Raster Calculator tool within the model builder environment. In this step, the scaling factor calculations were applied to each pixel value of the ST_B10 data, with the formula $\text{ProductID_ST_B10} * 0.00341802 + 149$ utilized to convert the surface temperature values to Kelvin units. By incorporating the scaling factor and additive offset into the calculation, the temperature values were accurately adjusted to the Kelvin scale.

Following the conversion of the ST_B10 data to Kelvin units, the processed files were automatically saved in a designated output folder with a naming convention that preserved the original ProductID information. The naming convention "%Name%.tif" was employed to save the converted temperature files, facilitating easy identification and organization of the output data for further analysis.

After, leveraging the shape file previously developed for Lake Gregory, the extraction of temperature values in "**Kelvin(K)**" for the Lake Gregory area was conducted using the "**Extract by Mask**" tool within the **ArcMap** environment and saved in another folder using the %Name%.tif extension same as before.

Figure 3. 15: Model for Surface Temperature and Extract by Lake Area

Surface temperature uncertainty is contained in ProductID_ST_QA with a Multiplicative Scale Factor of 0.01. The model (see Figure 3.16) was utilized to extract surface temperature uncertainty in the same manner as previously.

Figure 3. 16: Model for Surface Temperature Uncertainty and Extract by Lake Area

The integration of surface temperature and uncertainty data for each pixel involves a systematic approach to combine these essential datasets into a unified attribute table format.

To initiate the integration process, the uncertainty band data was first converted into point features using the raster-to-point tool. Then, the surface temperature data was converted into a geodatabase format to ensure compatibility and seamless integration within the analytical workflow. This conversion was essential to optimize the functionality and accessibility of the temperature data for further processing and analysis, particularly within the model builder framework as shown in Figure 3.17. To align each surface temperature file with its corresponding uncertainty file, a Python code snippet was employed to establish a matching mechanism based on the date information embedded within the file names. The expression demonstrates the Python code snippet:

```
r"C:\Users\Ishan\Desktop\LST  
folder\Temp.gdb\LC08_L2SP_141055_{0}_02_T1_ST_B10_TIF".format("%Name%"17:34)
```

Upon executing the matching process, the resulting point file containing the integrated surface temperature and uncertainty data was saved in a designated output folder. This consolidated dataset provided a comprehensive representation of temperature values and associated uncertainties at specific spatial locations, laying the foundation for advanced pixel-level analyses and assessments.

Figure 3. 17: Model for combining Surface Temperature Uncertainty as point files

In the process of identifying water pixels within the imagery dataset, the ProductID_QA_PIXEL was utilized to extract pertinent information related to pixel quality assessment. The CFMask algorithm output served as the input for the Quality Assessment Application, which computed various quality statistics based on the cloud mask and scene-specific information contained within the QA Band file. This file, formatted as an unsigned 16-bit Cloud-Optimized GeoTIFF (COG) image, shares the same spatial dimensions as the Level 1 (L1) scene data (Crawford et al., 2023).

The QA Band file incorporates quality metrics derived from the cloud mask analysis and scene statistics, providing valuable insights into the quality and reliability of the imagery data. Notably, the QA Band file includes bit-level information where specific artefacts are allocated to distinguish various pixel conditions. The least significant bit (Bit 0) is assigned

to represent the primary pixel condition, with subsequent bits encoding additional quality attributes (Crawford et al., 2023).

Given the diverse range of pixel quality classifications, the QA Band file offers a spectrum of confidence levels for each classification type. Table 3.2 outlines the specific bits within the QA Band file that correspond to distinct pixel conditions. For instance, 1 in the "fill" bit indicates that the associated L1 image bands contain fill data for the corresponding pixel, signifying potential data gaps or missing information (Crawford et al., 2023).

Furthermore, certain bits within the QA Band file are designated for specific quality assessments, such as Cloud Shadow Confidence, Snow/Ice Confidence, and Cirrus Confidence, allocated in bits 10-15. These reserved bits are earmarked for future enhancements and improvements in quality assessment methodologies, allowing for the incorporation of advanced algorithms and techniques to further refine pixel classification and quality evaluation (Crawford et al., 2023).

Table 3. 2: Landsat 8-9 Pixel Quality Assessment (QA_PIXEL) Bit Index (Crawford et al., 2023)

Bit	Flag Description	Values
0	Fill	0 for image data 1 for fill data
1	Dilated Cloud	0 for cloud is not dilated or no cloud 1 for cloud dilation
2	Cirrus	0 for Cirrus Confidence: no confidence level set or Low Confidence 1 for high confidence cirrus
3	Cloud	0 for cloud confidence is not high

		1 for high-confidence cloud
4	Cloud Shadow	0 for Cloud Shadow Confidence is not high 1 for high confidence cloud shadow
5	Snow	0 for Snow/Ice Confidence is not high 1 for high-confidence snow cover
6	Clear	0 if Cloud or Dilated Cloud bits are set 1 if Cloud and Dilated Cloud bits are not set
7	Water	0 for land or cloud 1 for water
8-9	Cloud Confidence	00 for no confidence level set 01 Low confidence 10 Medium confidence 11 High confidence
10-11	Cloud Shadow Confidence	00 for no confidence level set 01 Low confidence 10 Reserved 11 High confidence
12-13	Snow/Ice Confidence	00 for no confidence level set 01 Low confidence 10 Reserved 11 High confidence
14-15	Cirrus Confidence	00 for no confidence level set 01 Low confidence 10 Reserved 11 High confidence

The QA pixels from the ProductID_QA_PIXEL band were used to extract pixel values from the Lake Gregory Shapefile, which was converted into 16-bit binary data. For instance, considering values 21,824 and 21,952 from the scene.

LC08_L2SP_141055_20170318_20200904_02_T1_QA_PIXEL.TIF.tif (See Figure 3.18),

the conversion yielded binary representations of 0101010101000000 and 0101010111000000, respectively (Table 3.3), as per the encoding scheme outlined in Table 3.2.

Table 3. 3: Landsat 8-9 Pixel Quality Assessment (QA_PIXEL) Value Interpretations

Value	Fill	Dilated Cloud	Cirrus	Cloud	Cloud Shadow	Snow	Clear	Water	Cloud Confidence	Cloud Shadow Confidence	Snow/Ice Confidence	Cirrus Confidence	Pixel Description
21,824	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	Low	Low	Low	Low	Clear with lows set
21,952	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Low	Low	Low	Low	Water surface with lows set

Figure 3. 18: LC08_L2SP_141055_20170318_20200904_02_T1_QA_PIXEL.TIF.tif

The conversion of pixel values to binary data enabled a structured representation of pixel conditions, facilitating the identification of water pixels within the imagery dataset. By aligning the binary representations with the predefined classification types, water pixels were effectively distinguished from other pixel categories based on the quality statistics derived from the cloud mask and scene information.

The shape files containing water pixels (Converted to a polygon using the Raster to Polygon tool) were then utilized in a model, as depicted in Figure 3.19, to extract temperature points corresponding exclusively to water pixels. This targeted approach enabled the extraction of temperature data specifically from water pixel locations.

Figure 3. 19: Model for Extract water pixel temperatures from Temperature point files that include both uncertainty and ST

3.5 NASA Power Data Retrieval

Acquiring NASA Power meteorological data is a simple process that begins by navigating to the official NASA Power website at “<https://power.larc.nasa.gov/>”. Subsequently, users can access the API Services Catalogue to select the desired data parameters. In this instance, the focus is on utilizing the daily API to retrieve specific meteorological variables essential for developing a General Lake Model (GLM). The required parameters include Daily average shortwave radiation, cloud cover, Daily average air temperature 10m above the water surface, Daily average relative humidity (0-100%)10m above the water surface, Daily average wind speed 10m above the water surface, and Daily rainfall depth.

Upon selecting the desired parameters from the API Services Catalogue, users can proceed to specify the period and location for data retrieval. The chosen parameters align with the following definitions for the NASA Power API:

- ALLSKY_SFC_SW_DWN: CERES SYN1deg All Sky Surface Shortwave Downward Irradiance (W/m²)
- CLOUD_AMT: CERES SYN1deg Cloud Amount (%)
- T10M: MERRA-2 Temperature at 10 Meters (Celsius)
- RH2M: MERRA-2 Relative Humidity at 2 Meters (%)¹

¹ Used 2m RH instead of 10m upon data availability

- WS10M: MERRA-2 Wind Speed at 10 Meters (m/s)
- PRECTOTCORR: MERRA-2 Precipitation Corrected (mm/day)

Following the selection of parameters, proceed to download the data in CSV format for the specified period and location. This data retrieval process enables to access comprehensive meteorological information essential for developing a GLM model, which will be further discussed later.

3.6 Observed Climatic Data Retrieval

Developed a Python script that automates the process of scraping monthly climate data from the website “<https://en.tutiempo.net/> “. The data collection spans from January 1990 to December 2021. The methodology involved several key steps: generating URLs, scraping data, handling special HTML elements, and storing the data in a CSV file. (ANNEX 01)

3.6.1. URL Generation

The first step was to systematically generate URLs for each month and year within the specified date range. I created a function called `generate_urls` that takes a start date, an end date, and a base URL as inputs. This function initializes a date variable to the start date and iterates through each month until it reaches the end date. In each iteration, it formats the current month and year into a string and constructs the corresponding URL using the base URL. The constructed URLs are stored in a list, which was used later to fetch the web pages.

3.6.2. Data Scraping

The core of the data extraction process is handled by the `scrape_data` function. This function is responsible for fetching the content of each URL, processing the HTML to extract the relevant climate data, and returning the structured data. Here's how it works:

1. **HTTP Request and HTML Parsing:** The function uses the `requests` library to fetch the content of the web page for a given URL. It then uses the `BeautifulSoup` library to parse the HTML content.
2. **Span Class Handling:** The climate data tables include `span` elements with class names that map to specific content values. These mappings are defined in a style block within the HTML. To handle this, the function first extracts the style content and uses regular expressions (`re`-module) to create a dictionary (`mapper`) that maps each `span` class to its corresponding value.
3. **Replacing Span Elements:** Once the `mapper` is created, the function iterates over all `span` elements with classes present in the `mapper` and replaces them with their corresponding values. This ensures that the extracted data reflects the actual content.
4. **Extracting Table Data:** The function then locates the table containing the climate data using specific HTML classes. It extracts the headers from the table's header row and data from each subsequent row. Each row's data is cleaned and structured into a list, including the month and year for context.

3.6.3. Data Cleaning and Storage

After extracting and cleaning the data, it is stored in a CSV file. The `save_to_csv` function handles this process:

1. **File Writing:** The function opens a CSV file in write mode.
2. **Header and Data Writing:** It writes the extracted headers and data rows to the file using the `csv` library.
3. **File Encoding:** UTF-8 encoding is used to ensure compatibility and preserve data integrity.

3.6.4. Execution

The entire data collection process is orchestrated by the `main` function:

1. **Date Range Specification:** The function defines the start date and end date for the data collection.
2. **URL Generation:** It calls the `generate_urls` function to generate the list of URLs.
3. **Data Aggregation:** The function iterates over the generated URLs, calls `scrape_data` to extract data, and aggregates the results.
4. **Error Handling:** Any exceptions during the scraping process are caught and logged to ensure robustness.
5. **Data Saving:** Finally, the aggregated data is saved to a CSV file using the `save_to_csv` function.

Cloud cover monthly observed data for the Nuwara Eliya weather station from 2017 to 2020 was obtained from the Department of Meteorology, Sri Lanka.

3.7 Validation metrics

The comparison between NASA Power reanalysis data and observed data for the Nuwara Eliya weather station (Latitude: 6.96⁰, Longitude: 80.76⁰) from 1990 to 2021 involved assessing average monthly data from January 1990 to December 2021. Monthly data was derived from daily data (Deng et al., 2019) and observed missing days were removed from reanalysis data when producing monthly average data. The statistical indicators used for this evaluation included the Correlation Coefficient (r), Mean Error (ME), Relative Mean Error (RMSE), and Percent Bias (PBIAS) (Deng et al., 2019; Parsons et al., 2022). These metrics were employed to quantify the accuracy of the NASA Power Reanalysis data. The Correlation Coefficient (r) measures the linear correlation between satellite-based climatic variables and gauge observations, while PBIAS evaluates the systematic bias of satellite estimates. ME indicates the average difference, and RMSE measures the average error magnitude, giving more weight to larger errors relative to ME (Deng et al., 2019). The formulas for these statistical indices are detailed in the references provided.

$$r = \frac{\sum(X_i - \bar{X})(Y_i - \bar{Y})}{\sqrt{\sum(X_i - \bar{X})^2 \sum(Y_i - \bar{Y})^2}} \quad (9)$$

where X_i and Y_i are the individual sample points of observed and predicted values index with i . \bar{X} is the mean of X values, \bar{Y} is the mean of Y values.

$$ME = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (10)$$

Here n is the number of observations. y_i is the observed value and \hat{y}_i is the predicted value.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (11)$$

Here n is the number of observations. y_i is the observed value and \hat{y}_i is the predicted value.

$$PBIAS = 100 \times \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n y_i} \quad (12)$$

Where y_i is the observed value and \hat{y}_i is the predicted value.

3.8 Comparison of NASA POWER Reanalysis Data with Observed Meteorological Data

In this study, NASA POWER reanalysis data was compared with observed data for Nuwara Eliya across the four recognized rainfall seasons: the First Inter-Monsoon (March–April), Southwest Monsoon (May–September), Second Inter-Monsoon (October–November), and Northeast Monsoon (December–February). The comparison aimed to evaluate the accuracy and reliability of the reanalysis dataset in capturing seasonal rainfall variability in the Central Highlands. In addition to rainfall, key meteorological parameters, including average air temperature, wind speed, relative humidity, and cloud cover, were also

assessed based on monthly averages. Statistical metrics such as Correlation Coefficient (r), Mean Error (ME), Relative Mean Error (RMSE), and Percent Bias (PBIAS) were used to evaluate the agreement between NASA POWER data and observed records. This analysis provides insights into the applicability of NASA POWER data for hydrological and climatic studies in Nuwara Eliya of Sri Lanka.

3.9 GLM Setup

3.9.1. Overview

The setup and execution of the General Lake Model (GLM) involve the establishment of a structured framework to analyse lake dynamics and processes. In this research context, GLM version 3.0.5 was utilized within the R Studio environment to process data and derive insights. The essential components for running the GLM include the Configuration & Parameters defined in the "glm3.nml" file and Time Series Inputs stored in CSV format files. Upon completion of the GLM analysis, the results are typically saved in a NetCDF file format named output.nc. This file format allows for storing multidimensional lake data, facilitating further analysis, visualization, and sharing of the model outcomes. (see Figure 3.20)

Figure 3. 20: Flow diagram showing the files required for operation of the Model configuration & parameters: glm.nml

In the context of GLM model simulation, the primary configuration file, glm3.nml governs the settings and parameters of the simulation process. This file is interpreted as a text document by the GLM program, with its contents being sequentially read from the top to the bottom. Within the configuration file, distinct sections or 'blocks' encapsulate specific configuration options and parameters essential for defining the simulation setup. Each block within the glm3.nml file delineates a set of parameters that collectively influence the behaviour and outcomes of the GLM model simulation. In the course of the study, the configuration options and parameters are specified within the glm3.nml describes below (Hipsey, 2014). (See ANNEX 02 for Full version)

&glm_setup: General simulation info and mixing parameters

Within this section, specify the name of the lake, establish the upper limit for the number of layers within the surface layer, determine the minimum volume and thickness for layers,

and set the maximum thickness for the layers. The calibration of layer thickness was conducted manually to ensure standardization for comparative analysis across multiple lakes and was adjusted about the depth of the lake (Hipsey et al., 2019).

&light: lighting parameters

This section outlines the Light extinction coefficient (K_w), which determines the depth to which shortwave radiation penetrates the lake and is influenced by water clarity. A constant value for K_w was employed, and the Beer-Lambert law was utilized to model the heating of the surface layer by radiation (Hipsey et al., 2019).

&mixing: mixing parameters

In this section, the parameters for surface mixing are defined, The model operates on the principle that the balance between the available energy and the energy required for mixing determines the deepening rate of the surface mixed layer (SML), denoted as dz_{SML}/dt , where z_{SML} represents the depth from the surface to the bottom of the surface mixed layer. The available kinetic energy is computed based on contributions from various sources such as wind stirring, convective overturn, shear production between layers, and Kelvin–Helmholtz (K–H) billowing. Furthermore, the mixing below the thermocline in lakes, particularly in the deeper hypolimnion, is modelled using a characteristic vertical diffusivity. For the scenario of constant vertical diffusivity, Mixing efficiency - hypolimnetic turbulence is interpreted as the vertical diffusivity, and is uniformly applied below the surface mixed layer (Hipsey et al., 2019).

&morphometry: Lake morphometric information

In this section, outlined the hypsographic curve of the lake, along with specifying the longitude, latitude, and dimensions of the basin in terms of length and width at the crest level.

&time: Time controls

In this block, the parameters for the simulation time-period were established.

&output: Specification of output file details (depths, output frequency, and variables to write)

&init_profiles: Setting initial conditions (depth profiles) for temperature and salinity.

&sediment: Sediment heating

Within this segment, delineated the thermal characteristics of the soil/sediment layer situated beneath the lakebed. This encompassed detailing the heat conductivity, depth of the soil/sediment layer utilized for heat flux computations, the average annual sediment temperature, the amplitude of temperature fluctuations experienced in the sediment on a yearly basis, and the specific day of the year when the sediment temperature attains its maximum value (Hipsey et al., 2019).

3.9.2. Meteorological configuration and met.csv

In this study, obtained daily meteorological data from NASA Power, including shortwave radiation (W/m^2), cloud cover percentage, average daily temperature at 10m above the surface ($^{\circ}C$), daily average relative humidity (%), daily average wind speed at 10m above the water surface, and daily rainfall depth. The “rad_mode” parameter was set to “0” based on the guidelines provided in reference (Hipsey, 2014). After experimentation, it was determined that “cloud_mode” option “3” yielded superior results compared to other options. The “albedo_mode” was configured as option “2”, as it required only the solar zenith angle for albedo calculations. For longwave radiation calculations, “lw_type” was designated as “LW_CC”, utilizing cloud cover data. The bulk-transfer coefficients for momentum (CD), sensible heat (CH), and latent heat (CE) were assumed to be relatively constant over the 5-year simulation period. The atmospheric stability parameter “atm_stab” was set to mode “0”. Due to the unavailability of wind sheltering data, this factor was disregarded in the simulations.

3.10 GLM in R

The General Lake Model (GLM) Version 3.0.5 was implemented in the R Studio for model execution. The ‘GLM3r’ package, along with ‘rLakeAnalyzer’ and ‘glmtools’ libraries, was utilized to facilitate the operation of GLM in the R environment. For data visualization and plotting, the ‘tidyverse’ library was employed. The complete code details are provided in Annex 03.

3.11 GLM Model Calibration

The initial step in parameter calibration involved performing a sensitivity analysis by adjusting each variable in the nml file by +20% and -20% increments, assessing the resulting impact on the root mean square error (RMSE) of surface temperature. Subsequently, the parameters exhibiting the highest sensitivity were selected for further refinement using an automated calibration algorithm integrated into the General Lake Model (GLM) (Bruce et al., 2018).

4. CHAPER 4: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Evaluating NASA Power Reanalysis Data

4.1.1. Precipitation

In this study, the observed precipitation data obtained from "<https://en.tutiempo.net/>" underwent a data cleaning process where missing days were removed from the NASA Power reanalysis data before calculating the monthly totals from the daily data. Following the guidelines provided by the Natural Resources Conservation Service National Water and Climate Centre, the United States Department of Agriculture (U.S. Department of Agriculture, 2024), only months with more than 25 days of observed data were selected for calculating the total monthly precipitation. It was observed that every year from 2009 onwards had months with continuous observations exceeding 25 days. Monthly data from 2009 to 2021 was utilized for further comparative analysis.

When comparing the average monthly precipitation data (see Figure 4.1), it was observed that the NASA Power reanalysis data tended to overestimate precipitation values from January to April, followed by underestimations from June to August, and subsequent overestimations from October to December. This pattern was identified through a comparative analysis of the observed and reanalysis data. The discrepancy in precipitation estimates across different months highlight the need for further investigation into the accuracy and reliability of the reanalysis data.

Figure 4. 1: Average monthly Observed Precipitation vs NASA power Precipitation data

The analysis of monthly data scales for each season (see Figure 4.2) revealed distinct patterns in the correlation and bias of NASA Power reanalysis data compared to observed data. During the first inter-monsoon (FIM) season, a strong correlation coefficient of 0.83 was observed, indicating a good linear relationship. However, the PBIAS value of 55.52% indicated a significant overestimation of precipitation values by the NASA Power reanalysis data during this period. In contrast, the southwest monsoon (SWM) period exhibited a correlation coefficient of 0.74, with a PBIAS of -10.86%, indicating an acceptable level of underestimation. The second inter-monsoon (SIM) period showed a correlation coefficient of 0.73 and a PBIAS of 25.47%, indicating a fair match with observed values. Lastly, during the northeast monsoon (NEM) season, a strong correlation coefficient of 0.95 was observed, with a PBIAS of 25.88%, indicating a fair value. These results highlight the varying performance of the NASA Power reanalysis data across different seasons and underscore

the importance of considering both correlation and bias metrics in evaluating the accuracy of the reanalysis data.

Figure 4. 2: Seasonal Comparison of Monthly Observed Precipitation and NASA Power Precipitation Data

In the comparative analyses conducted for each month (see Figure 4.3), distinct patterns were observed across different seasons. During the first inter-monsoon (FIM) season, the months of March and April exhibited a high correlation coefficient of 0.83 and 0.80,

respectively. However, a notable overestimation was observed during these months, with a high PBIAS of 45.47% in March and 61.47% in April. In the southwest monsoon (SWM) season, the five months from May showed a strong correlation coefficient of 0.92 and a minimal PBIAS of 3.14%, indicating a robust match with observed data. Conversely, the months of June, July, and August displayed decreasing correlations of 0.84, 0.65, and 0.24, respectively, with PBIAS values indicating underestimations of precipitation. Notably, August exhibited the weakest predictions with no correlation. September, the last month of the SWM season, demonstrated a strong correlation of 0.81 and a PBIAS of 4.28%, signifying a robust relationship with observed values. In the second inter-monsoon (SIM) season, October exhibited a very strong correlation of 0.87 and a PBIAS of 9.61%, while November showed a decrease in correlation to 0.64 and a large overestimation with a PBIAS of 44.09%. Lastly, In the northeast monsoon (NEM) season, a three-month period starting from December exhibited a strong correlation of 0.94 and a PBIAS of 22.39%, indicating overestimation. In January and February, there was a very strong correlation of 0.94 and 0.96, respectively, with fair PBIAS values indicating overestimations of 26.49% and 33.88%.

The observed patterns indicate that while the Reanalysis data performs well in certain months, especially during the early SWM and NEM seasons, there are notable periods where the accuracy of reanalysis data diminishes, particularly in the mid to late SWM season and the latter part of the SIM season. These findings underscore the necessity for targeted bias correction efforts to address overestimation during the FIM and certain NEM

months, as well as underestimation during the SWM. Additionally, improving the NASA power reanalysis precipitation data adaptability to varying seasonal dynamics could enhance overall predictive accuracy.

In conclusion, the NASA Power precipitation data demonstrates a strong potential for accurate precipitation prediction, with specific areas identified for further refinement. Addressing the biases and enhancing the correlation during the identified weaker periods will be crucial steps toward developing a more robust and reliable reanalysis data tool.

Figure 4. 3: Monthly Comparison of Monthly Observed Precipitation and NASA Power Precipitation Data

4.1.2. Average Temperature

The comparison between observed data and NASA power temperature data focuses on months with more than 21 days of observations to calculate average monthly temperatures (U.S. Department of Agriculture, 2024). The analysis spans from 2009 to 2021, revealing a visible shift in the NASA power data, attributed to a scaling factor. To address this disagreement, a simple bias correction method was applied to each month's data, as detailed in Table 4.1.

Figure 4. 4: Average monthly Observed Temperature vs NASA power Temperature Data

Following the implementation of bias correction for each month's temperatures, a comprehensive evaluation was conducted to assess the impact of the correction on the dataset. This evaluation aimed to analyse the effectiveness of the bias correction method in aligning the observed temperatures with the NASA power temperature data. The post-

bias correction evaluation involved a detailed examination of the monthly temperature data from the selected period.

Table 4. 1: Temperature Bias Correction

Month	Observed Average Temperature	NASA power Average Temperature Data	Bias
1	14.91	21.22	-6.31
2	15.51	21.93	-6.42
3	16.32	23.12	-6.80
4	16.95	24.05	-7.10
5	17.21	23.70	-6.50
6	16.33	22.98	-6.65
7	16.01	22.58	-6.58
8	15.92	22.54	-6.62
9	15.95	22.63	-6.69
10	16.04	22.70	-6.66
11	15.88	22.28	-6.40
12	15.41	21.75	-6.34

Based on the findings depicted in Figure 4.5, a robust correlation of $r = 0.89$ is observed alongside minimal mean error (ME) of 0.26 and root mean square error (RMSE) of 0.34. These results indicate that the interpretation of NASA power reanalysis data is highly favourable and indicative of its quality and reliability.

Following the bias correction process illustrated in Figure 4.5, it is evident that all months exhibit a notable concordance with the observed values, characterized by mean error (ME) below 0.38 and root mean square error (RMSE) under 0.57. February stands out with the highest ME and RMSE values, while July demonstrates the lowest ME. Conversely, August

showcases the minimum RMSE value. Despite August displaying lower accuracy in precipitation data generation, NASA power temperature data exhibits superior precision in data production.

Figure 4. 5: Scatter plot of Observed average Temperatures and NASA Power Bias corrected average temperature values from 2009 to 2021

Figure 4. 6: Monthly Comparison of Monthly Observed Average Temperatures and NASA Power Bias Corrected Average Temperatures

4.1.3. Average Wind Speed

Computation of the mean monthly wind speeds was done using data points exceeding 21 days for each month. Subsequently, the average monthly wind speeds were calculated for the period spanning from 2009 to 2021. The comparison presented in Figure 4.7 illustrates a strong correlation between the calculated average wind speeds and the observed values, indicating a robust relationship between the two datasets.

Figure 4. 7: Average monthly Observed Wind Speed vs NASA power Wind Speed

The data depicted in Figure 4.8 reveals a significant correlation between the NASA power wind speed data and the observed monthly values, with a correlation coefficient (r) of 0.83. The mean error (ME) of 0.62 and root mean square error (RMSE) of 0.77 further support this strong correlation, indicating a robust relationship between the NASA power wind speed data and the actual observed values.

The analysis presented in Figure 4.9 indicates that for each month, the mean error (ME) values are below 1.0 and the root mean square error (RMSE) values are under 1.11. May exhibits the weakest performance with ME at 1.0 and RMSE at 1.11, suggesting a consistent overestimation of average wind speed by NASA's power data across most years, except for 2009 and 2021. Conversely, March stands out with the most accurate performance, boasting an ME of 0.31 and demonstrating a strong correlation with the monthly wind speed for each year. In general, NASA's power data could serve as a viable alternative data source due to its overall satisfactory level of accuracy.

Figure 4. 8: Scatter plot of monthly Observed average Wind Speed and NASA Power Wind Speed values from 2009 to 2021

Figure 4. 9: Monthly Comparison of Monthly Observed Average Wind Speed and NASA Power Wind Speed

4.1.4. Average Relative Humidity

The evaluation comparing the observed data with NASA power Average Relative humidity data concentrates on months where observations exceed 21 days to compute the mean monthly Relative humidity. The assessment encompasses the years 2009 to 2021 and reveals notable deviations from observed values particularly in January, February, and March, as illustrated in Figure 4.10.

Figure 4. 10: Average monthly Observed RH vs NASA RH

The data presented in Figure 4.11 indicates a reasonable correlation of $r = 0.76$ between the observed data and NASA power Relative humidity data. However, the mean error (ME) of 4.51 and root mean square error (RMSE) of 6.22 are relatively elevated. In comparison to other parameters under evaluation, Relative humidity demonstrates the least robust relationship with the observed data.

The analysis depicted in Figure 4.12 reveals notable discrepancies in the first three months, namely January, February, and March, concerning Relative Humidity (RH) values when compared to observed data. Specifically, January exhibits a mean error (ME) of 8.05 and a root mean square error (RMSE) of 8.83, February shows an ME of 10.53 and an RMSE of 11.43, and March displays an ME of 10.18 and an RMSE of 11.33, indicating an overestimation of RH values by NASA power during these months. Subsequently, from April to December, all months demonstrate lower ME and RMSE values. Overall, while NASA power data tends to overestimate RH values during the initial months, it aligns more closely with observed data from April to December.

Figure 4. 11: Scatter plot of monthly Observed average RH and NASA Power RH values from 2009 to 2021

Figure 4. 12: Monthly Comparison of Monthly Observed Average Relative Humidity and NASA Power Relative Humidity

4.1.5. Cloud Cover

The absence of observed cloud cover data on <https://en.tutiempo.net/> necessitated the acquisition of such data from the Department of Meteorology in Sri Lanka. By leveraging the monthly average observed data provided by the Department for the period spanning from May 2017 to July 2020, a comparison was made between the observed cloud cover data and the NASA Power reanalysis data. The analysis, as depicted in Figure 4.13, underscores a robust correlation between the observed data and the NASA Power reanalysis data for each month, highlighting the reliability and consistency of the NASA Power reanalysis data in capturing cloud cover dynamics during the specified timeframe.

Figure 4. 13: Monthly Observed Average Cloud Cover and NASA Power Cloud Cover

The data analysis was further scrutinized through a static examination using the scatter plot depicted in Figure 4.14. The results revealed a robust correlation coefficient of 0.92,

accompanied by a mean error (ME) of 0.4 and a root mean square error (RMSE) of 0.5, indicating a strong correlation within the dataset. This statistical analysis, as visualized in the scatter plot, underscores the reliability and coherence of the data, emphasizing the strength of the relationship between the variables under consideration.

Figure 4. 14: Scatter plot of monthly Observed average Cloud Cover and NASA Power Cloud Cover values from 2017 to 2020

The assessment of NASA Power data for various meteorological parameters, such as precipitation, wind speed, relative humidity, and cloud cover, is essential for determining its suitability for integration into the General Lake Model (GLM) to model Lake surface temperature accurately. While most parameters in the data showed reasonable accuracy, a significant anomaly was detected in the average temperature data, necessitating a

correction due to a vertical shift. This discovery is consistent with a study conducted in Indonesia (Figure 4.15) (Darman et al., 2024), which also noted temperature discrepancies in weather station data, highlighting the critical need to identify and rectify such anomalies before using NASA Power average temperature data for modelling Lake surface temperature or any other use.

Figure 4. 15: Temperature comparison of 4 different weather stations (Darman et al., 2024)

4.2 Evaluating Landsat Surface Temperature Product-Derived Lake Surface Temperatures

After implementing the prescribed methods outlined in the methodology, a total of 38 scenes of Lake surface temperature were obtained, as detailed in Table 4.2. The lake area comprises 488 pixels, with specific identification of water pixels conducted based on QA_PIXEL values to uphold data quality standards. Subsequently, water pixels deemed unsatisfactory in Landsat scenes were excluded from the analysis to ensure the integrity and reliability of the dataset used for further examination and interpretation. Given the

utilization of satellite imagery for deriving Lake surface temperature values, challenges arise in the presence of clouds, as they can obstruct the satellite's view of the actual surface, leading to inaccuracies in temperature predictions. Cloud cover tends to result in significantly lower "surface" temperature estimates due to the cooler nature of clouds compared to the true surface temperature. This discrepancy can be substantial, reaching tens of Kelvin, particularly in scenarios with extensive cloud cover, especially high-altitude clouds with markedly lower temperatures than the surface. Notably, when clouds are in proximity but not directly above the area of interest, the prediction of Lake surface temperature tends to notably underestimate the actual temperature. These general observations prompted an exploration into the relationship between cloud proximity and the error in Lake surface temperature, which could find in the uncertainty in error quantified in the ST_QA band (Laraby et al., 2016), which was utilized to uphold data quality. In the absence of measured data for comparison, the selected data was used to calibrate and validate GLM model, accompanied by average uncertainty values, to further enhance the quality and reliability of the dataset.

Table 4. 2: Landsat Surface Temperature Product Derived Lake Surface Temperatures

Date	Average Temperature (°C)	Number of water Pixels	Average uncertainty (K)	Remark
20170318	22.7	433	3.3	
20170419	25.2	12	3.5	Removed
20170809	21.6	411	2.8	
20171231	22.2	429	3.8	
20180116	16.8	1	3.2	Removed

20180201	22.8	34	6.9	Removed
20180217	21.9	419	3.9	
20180305	25.0	420	4.1	
20180321	23.8	393	3.8	
20180422	24.2	225	2.5	
20180508	26.0	246	4.7	
20180913	19.9	109	5.7	Removed
20181015	22.5	255	5.7	
20181116	23.6	354	4.6	
20181202	21.4	428	3.9	
20190103	22.4	423	3.8	
20190220	20.8	398	3.9	
20190308	23.9	400	2.6	
20190324	23.1	365	3.5	
20190409	26.6	13	5.5	Removed
20190511	24.6	38	4.1	Removed
20190628	21.6	2	4.1	Removed
20190730	18.8	378	3.9	
20200310	24.0	394	3.8	
20200411	26.3	2	3.3	Removed
20200529	18.2	30	5.7	Removed
20201020	20.9	385	4.8	
20201207	23.4	412	2.9	
20210124	19.8	397	3.8	
20210209	20.5	400	3.9	
20210225	23.3	392	3.8	
20210313	22.1	366	4.2	
20210329	24.5	307	3.5	
20210414	24.0	93	4.9	Removed
20210601	17.0	65	5.8	Removed
20210719	19.8	49	6.2	Removed
20210820	21.3	287	4.6	
20211226	19.7	367	4.1	

4.3 Lake surface temperatures modelled by the General Lake Model (GLM)

4.3.1. Sensitivity analysis

Following the initial model run with default parameters, a sensitivity analysis was conducted to assess the impact of parameter variations on the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) values of surface temperatures. The sensitivity indices were calculated according to Equation 12, and the results are presented in Table 4.3. Subsequently, specific parameters were selected for the calibration process, excluding the scaling factor sensitivity, such as `wind_factor`, `sw_factor`, `at_factor`, `rh_factor`, `rain_factor`, and `lw_factor`, to mitigate significant variations in the final output temperatures. It was assumed that the climatic data used exhibited good accuracy. The calibration parameters for further refinement included `ce`, `sed_heat_Ksoil`, `sed_temp_peak_doy`, `Kw`, `sed_temp_mean`, `sed_temp_depth`, and `ch`. This selection aimed to optimize the model calibration process and enhance the accuracy of the Lake surface temperature predictions.

$$SI = \frac{\left(\frac{\text{Output}_{\text{new}} - \text{Output}_{\text{original}}}{\text{Output}_{\text{original}}} \right)}{\left(\frac{\text{Parameter}_{\text{new}} - \text{Parameter}_{\text{original}}}{\text{Parameter}_{\text{original}}} \right)} \quad (13)$$

Table 4. 3: Sensitivity Analysis

Parameter	Original Value	-20%	20%	RMSE	RMSE (-20%)	RMSE (+20%)	SI (-20%)	SI (+20%)
Kw	2.9	2.32	3.48	2.65	2.6	2.68	0.094	0.057
coef_mix_conv	0.2	0.16	0.24	2.65	2.66	2.65	-0.019	0
coef_wind_stir	0.3	0.24	0.36	2.65	2.66	2.68	-0.019	0.057
coef_mix_shear	0.1	0.08	0.12	2.65	2.65	2.67	0	0.038
coef_mix_turb	0.45	0.36	0.54	2.65	2.68	2.68	-0.057	0.057
coef_mix_KH	0.2	0.16	0.24	2.65	2.66	2.67	-0.019	0.038
coef_mix_hyp	0.5	0.4	0.6	2.65	2.68	2.65	-0.057	0
wind_factor	1	0.8	1.2	2.65	2.3	3.18	0.660	1
sw_factor	1	0.8	1.2	2.65	2.59	2.7	0.113	0.094
lw_factor	1	0.8	1.2	2.65	3.84	2.69	-2.245	0.075
at_factor	1	0.8	1.2	2.65	4.43	2.16	-3.358	-0.924
rh_factor	1	0.8	1.2	2.65	3.99	2.11	-2.528	-1.019
rain_factor	1	0.8	1.2	2.65	3.08	2.26	-0.811	-0.736
cd	0.0013	0.00104	0.00156	2.65	2.67	2.65	-0.038	0
ce	0.0035	0.0028	0.0042	2.65	2.28	3.21	0.698	1.057
ch	0.003	0.0024	0.0036	2.65	2.68	2.61	-0.057	-0.075
rain_threshold	0.025	0.02	0.03	2.65	2.67	2.68	-0.038	0.057
runoff_coef	0.08	0.064	0.096	2.65	2.94	2.66	-0.547	0.019
sed_heat_Ksoil	2.9	2.32	3.48	2.65	2.68	2.86	-0.057	0.396
sed_temp_depth	0.2	0.16	0.24	2.65	2.83	2.59	-0.339	-0.113
sed_temp_mean	15	12	18	2.65	2.68	2.61	-0.057	-0.075
sed_temp_mean.01	17	13.6	20.4	2.65	2.78	2.65	-0.245	0
sed_temp_mean.02	20	16	24	2.65	2.78	2.65	-0.245	0
sed_temp_amplitude	8	6.4	9.6	2.65	2.55	2.78	0.189	0.245
sed_temp_amplitude.01	10	8	12	2.65	2.68	2.65	-0.057	0
sed_temp_amplitude.02	12	9.6	14.4	2.65	2.66	2.68	-0.019	0.057
sed_temp_peak_doy	130	104	156	2.65	2.4	2.91	0.472	0.491
sed_temp_peak_doy.01	120	96	144	2.65	2.65	2.65	0	0
sed_temp_peak_doy.02	110	88	132	2.65	2.68	2.68	-0.057	0.057
zone_heights	0.35	0.28	0.42	2.65	2.65	2.65	0	0
zone_heights.01	0.6	0.48	0.72	2.65	2.65	2.65	0	0
zone_heights.02	1	0.8	1.2	2.65	2.65	2.68	0	0.057
sed_reflectivity	0.1	0.08	0.12	2.65	2.67	2.66	-0.038	0.019
sed_reflectivity.01	0.01	0.008	0.012	2.65	2.68	2.65	-0.057	0
sed_reflectivity.02	0.01	0.008	0.012	2.65	2.65	2.68	0	0.057

sed_roughness	0.1	0.08	0.12	2.65	2.68	2.68	-0.057	0.057
sed_roughness.01	0.01	0.008	0.012	2.65	2.68	2.65	-0.057	0
sed_roughness.02	0.01	0.008	0.012	2.65	2.65	2.78	0	0.245

4.3.2. Model Calibration and Validation

The calibration process involved the utilization of an automatic calibration method integrated into the GLM3r package. The variable selected for calibration was temperature, with specific calibration parameters identified and their respective ranges detailed in Table 4.4. The optimization method chosen was CMA-ES, with the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) serving as the metric for calibration. A target fit of 2.0 was set, and the calibration process spanned 2000 iterations. The model surface temperature at 0m depth was selected for calibration and validation against Landsat Collection 2 Level 2 surface temperature products, as Landsat's thermal infrared sensors capture the skin temperature of the water surface (~top 1 mm) (Landsat, 2022). While the GLM model does not explicitly resolve the skin layer, its uppermost computational layer represents the bulk surface temperature (typically within the top 10 cm), making $z = 0\text{m}$ the best available approximation for comparison. The calibration period was defined from January 1, 2017, to December 31, 2018, while the validation period was extended from January 1, 2019, to December 31, 2021. This meticulous calibration approach aimed to enhance the accuracy and reliability of the model's temperature predictions by iteratively adjusting the selected parameters within the specified ranges using an automated optimization method.

Table 4. 4: Calibration Parameters

Parameters	Lower Value	Upper Value	Initial Value
sed_temp_peak_doy	60	130	130
sed_temp_peak_doy.1	110	150	120
sed_temp_peak_doy.2	100	140	110
ce	0.001	0.0035	0.0035
Kw	0.3	2.9	2.9
ch	0.003	0.005	0.0030
sed_temp_depth	0.2	0.6	0.2
sed_temp_mean.1	15	30	15
sed_temp_mean.2	15	25	17
sed_temp_mean	15	25	20
sed_heat_Ksoil	1	2.9	2.9

The optimization of the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) value across varying numbers of iterations is visually depicted in Figure 4.16, illustrating the iterative process of refining the model to minimize prediction errors. The final calibrated parameters resulting from this optimization process are presented in Table 4.5, encapsulating the optimized values that best fit the model to the observed data.

Figure 4. 16: Optimization Using CMA-ES For Temperature

Table 4. 5: Calibrated Final Parameters

sed_temp_peak_doy	60
sed_temp_peak_doy.1	119.51
sed_temp_peak_doy.2	140
ce	0.0032
Kw	1.1653
ch	0.005
sed_temp_depth	0.6
sed_temp_mean	16.98
sed_temp_mean.1	19.13
sed_temp_mean.2	21.94
sed_heat_Ksoil	1.28

Throughout the calibration phase, the model exhibited a Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of 2.15 and a correlation coefficient of 0.65, indicating the agreement between the model's predictions and the actual data during this period. Subsequently, during the validation

phase, the model maintained an RMSE of 2.17 with a correlation coefficient of 0.65, reflecting the model's performance in predicting outcomes on new data. The overall assessment of the model encompassing both calibration and validation periods revealed an RMSE of 2.02 and a correlation coefficient of 0.73, suggesting the model's general predictive accuracy across the entire dataset. These comparative metrics are visually represented in Figure 4.17.

An additional dataset was obtained from the Department of Irrigation, Sri Lanka, comprising 8 measurements conducted between 2017 and 2021. These measurements were utilized solely to visually compare validated models due to the limited number of sampling points, precluding the possibility of performing statistical analyses. The comparison, as illustrated in Figure 4.18, indicates a substantial level of agreement between the majority of data points and the calibrated model. This visual assessment serves as a qualitative validation of the model's performance when applied to the new dataset, highlighting the effectiveness of the model in capturing the underlying patterns within the data.

Figure 4. 17: Calibrated GLM simulation (Black Line) of LST and Landsat LST (Red Dots)

Figure 4. 18: Calibrated GLM simulation (Black Line) of LST and Measured water temperatures by Department of Irrigation (Red Dots)

When comparing the observed data from the irrigation department, it was noted that on July 31, 2018, the temperature was recorded at 17°C, and on September 20, 2020, it was

16°C minimum surface temperature values. These temperatures match the model result well. In the context of Gregory Lake, the municipality of Nuwara Eliya opens the bottom outlet gate during periods of excess rainfall to mitigate flooding upstream of the lake. This action is not governed by a specific pattern or schedule based on rainfall; rather, it is implemented reactively on days when deemed necessary. According to reference (Mi et al., 2019), the process of bottom withdrawal results in the cooling of surface temperatures in a water body by extracting cooler, denser water from the lower layers, thereby allowing warmer water to remain in the upper layers initially. As time progresses, the retained heat at the surface dissipates into the atmosphere, particularly if the surrounding air is cooler. Moreover, bottom withdrawal restricts the mixing between different water layers, preventing the warmer lower water from blending with the surface water. Consequently, the surface water loses heat more rapidly, leading to a gradual decrease in surface temperatures over time.

The outflow from Lake Gregory was estimated using the Area-ratio method (Gianfagna et al., 2015), utilizing a measuring gauge located downstream of Nanu Oya, with data sourced from the Ceylon Electricity Board (CEB) measuring gauge. By comparing the outflow data with surface temperature, as depicted in Figure 4.19, there are indications that the outflow may contribute to lower temperatures. However, due to the absence of documented evidence regarding the specific days or times of outlet openings, further investigation is necessary to delve deeper into this matter. For this research, a closed basin approach was

adopted to provide a reasonable estimation of surface temperature variations, demonstrating commendable seasonal variability.

Figure 4. 19: Calibrated GLM simulation (Black Line) of LST, Measured water temperatures by Department of Irrigation (Brown Dots), Landsat LST (Red Dots) and outflow (Blue line)

Although depth-specific temperature validation was not conducted in this study, Figure 4.20 serves as a reference for the model output, illustrating the depth-specific temporal variations in water temperature.

Figure 4. 20: GLM simulation of Temperature Variations

4.4 Climate Change scenarios

4.4.1. Introduction

The analysis was conducted using the General Lake Model (GLM), focusing on lake surface water temperature. Average air temperatures were varied from the baseline climatic conditions, with average air temperatures ranging through +5°C (hot), +2.5°C (warm), -2.5°C (cool), and -5°C (cold). These temperature variations reflected potential impacts of changing degree-day accumulations on lake thermal dynamics.

Solar radiation was adjusted with percentage deviations of +50% (very high-sunny), +25% (high), -25% (low), and -50% (very low-cloudy). Similarly, precipitation levels were modified by +50% (very wet), +25% (wet), -25% (dry), and -50% (very dry). In addition to these

scenarios, wind speed was varied by +50% (high wind), +25% (windy), -25% (low wind), and -50% (very low wind) to examine its influence on lake mixing and heat exchange processes.

This approach generated 256 climatic scenarios to evaluate the combined effects of temperature, solar radiation, precipitation, and wind on lake surface water temperature. Relative humidity was kept constant due to uncertainties decreasing or increasing precipitation amounts and temperatures.

The climatic scenarios selected for this analysis were chosen to reflect a broad range of plausible climate conditions that could significantly influence lake thermal dynamics and the degree-day accumulations. The variations in air temperature (+5°C to -5°C) were designed to capture extreme temperature shifts that might occur under climate change scenarios, ranging from hotter to cooler conditions. These shifts are particularly relevant for understanding changes in lake water temperature under warming or cooling trends.

The adjustments in solar radiation (from +50% to -50%) reflect the potential effects of changes in cloud cover and atmospheric conditions, which can influence the amount of solar energy received by the lake surface. These scenarios address the impact of very sunny to very cloudy conditions, providing insight into the varying energy inputs and their effects on lake temperature.

Precipitation variations (+50% to -50%) were chosen to simulate different rainfall scenarios, ranging from very wet to very dry conditions, to explore the role of precipitation in heat exchange and lake mixing. Increased precipitation can affect the water column structure

and influence temperature distribution, while reduced rainfall could result in reduced lake volume and increased evaporation, further affecting thermal dynamics.

Lastly, variations in wind speed (+50% to -50%) were selected to examine how changes in lake mixing and heat exchange processes due to wind intensity could affect surface temperatures. Winds play a crucial role in thermal stratification and vertical mixing, with higher wind speeds promoting mixing of the surface and deeper waters, while lower wind speeds could enhance stratification and limit heat exchange.

These selected scenarios collectively provide a comprehensive understanding of how variations in key climate factors could alter lake surface temperatures and thermal behaviour under different climate conditions (Terjung et al., 1984).

4.4.2. Results

The Figure 4.21 shows the variation in surface water temperature over time, comparing the baseline scenario to all climatic scenarios. The baseline scenario, depicted by a black line, serves as a reference to evaluate the impacts of different climatic variations. Other lines, which represent various climatic scenarios. These scenarios are shown in different colours (refer Annex 04)

Figure 4. 21: Monthly Average Surface Water Temperature variation for all scenarios

The analysis of monthly deviations in lake surface temperature under different climatic scenarios reveals distinct patterns across Nuwara Eliya climate seasons. By identifying the scenario with the highest temperature deviation for each month (Figure 4.22), insights into the interactions between air temperature, solar radiation, wind speed, and rainfall are clarified.

Figure 4. 22: Climatic scenarios with the maximum lake surface temperature deviations (Compared to baseline condition)

4.4.3. Dominant Scenario Patterns

The scenario `air_5_shortwave_1.5_wind_0.5_rain_0.5`, characterized by a 5°C increase in air temperature, a 1.5x increase in solar radiation, a 50% reduction in wind speed, and a 50% reduction in rainfall, emerges as dominant during most months. These months, particularly January through April, October, November, and December, experience significant warming due to reduced wind speeds and enhanced solar radiation, which amplify the effects of elevated air temperature.

For example, in March and April, maximum deviations of 10.83°C and 11.09°C, respectively, suggest that limited wind speeds impede heat dissipation, allowing surface temperatures to spike.

However, during the Southwest Monsoon (May–September), the scenario `air_5_shortwave_1.5_wind_0.5_rain_1.5` dominates, with deviations ranging from 8.16°C to 9.28°C. Interestingly, increased rainfall (+50%) during these months contributes to the largest temperature deviations, emphasizing that high rainfall alone does not mitigate warming effectively when combined with reduced wind speeds and high air temperatures. January, however, is the sole month where a +25% increase in rainfall contributes to the maximum temperature deviation, reflecting unique interactions between rainfall and other climatic factors during this period.

4.4.4. Seasonal Variability and Impacts

- **First Inter-monsoon (March–April):** The highest deviations occur during this period, driven by elevated temperatures, intense solar radiation, and minimal wind. A 50% reduction in rainfall amplifies temperature deviations by limiting evaporative cooling. April records the peak deviation of 11.09°C, underscoring the critical impact of rainfall reduction during this season.
- **Southwest Monsoon (May–September):** This period showcases a unique interaction where increased rainfall (+50%) coincides with the largest temperature deviations for all months within this monsoon. High rainfall during these months,

while increasing evaporative cooling, appears insufficient to counteract the warming effects of reduced wind speeds and elevated air temperatures. These findings underscore the complex interplay of rainfall and wind patterns during this period.

- **Second Inter-monsoon (October–November):** This period is marked by the highest monthly rainfall totals (October: 251.27 mm, November: 213.87 mm). However, deviations persist (9.49°C and 9.77°C) due to reduced wind speeds. Rainfall, though abundant, does not significantly alter the dominant warming effect, suggesting that during these months, the cooling impact of rainfall is outweighed by the combined effects of air temperature and solar radiation.
- **Northeast Monsoon (December–February):** Like the first inter-monsoon, this season is characterized by moderate rainfall and reduced wind speeds. For January and February, deviations of 9.32°C and 9.66°C suggest that rainfall reduction plays a limited role in temperature regulation, as solar radiation and wind speed reductions dominate.

4.4.5. Key Climatic Drivers

The analysis of 256 scenarios reveals that the impact of rainfall varies significantly across months:

- **Rainfall:** While a 50% reduction in rainfall coincides with the largest temperature deviations for some months (e.g., March, April), other months exhibit maximum deviations under increased rainfall scenarios (e.g., May: +50%, January: +25%). This variability suggests that the influence of rainfall is contingent on seasonal dynamics, such as baseline rainfall levels and interactions with wind-driven mixing. High rainfall during certain months may not offset warming due to limited wind mixing, whereas during other months, increased rainfall aids in reducing warming through evaporative cooling.
- **Wind Speed:** As shown in Figure 4.23 strong negative correlation (-0.87) with temperature deviations underscores its consistent role in promoting thermal mixing and dissipating heat. Reduced wind speeds during transitional periods exacerbate warming, regardless of rainfall variability.
- **Air Temperature and Solar Radiation:** These remain the primary drivers across all seasons, with consistent contributions to surface warming irrespective of rainfall or wind speed changes.

Figure 4. 23: Relationship between Wind Speed and Maximum Lake Surface Temperature Deviations

4.4.6. Implications for Lake Management

The findings highlight the importance of considering seasonal variability and interactions between climatic drivers:

During the **first inter-monsoon** and **second inter-monsoon**, targeted interventions like enhancing wind-driven mixing or artificial aeration could mitigate the stratification caused by reduced wind speeds. The **southwest monsoon** demonstrates the potential for leveraging natural rainfall variability to offset warming. Strategies to optimize water retention and cooling during this season could be prioritized. During the **northeast monsoon**, efforts should focus on managing solar radiation impacts, as rainfall reductions during this period have a limited influence on mitigating warming.

5. CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSION AND LIMITATIONS WITH FURTHER STUDIES

In this study, employed the General Lake Model (GLM) to simulate the daily Lake Surface Water Temperature (LSWT) of Lake Gregory, using a closed basin approach due to the unavailability of inflow and outflow data. The model was driven by meteorological inputs from NASA's POWER reanalysis dataset. Validated the simulations against the Landsat 2 Collection 2 surface temperature product. Finally, the validated model was used to assess the potential impacts of climate change on Lake Gregory's LSWT.

5.1 Conclusion

- The NASA Power Reanalysis data exhibits a strong correlation with precipitation, with a tendency to overestimate values from January to April, underestimate from June to August, and overestimate again from October to December. Seasonal assessment reveals high accuracy during the Northeast Monsoon (NEM) season but lower accuracy during the Second Inter-Monsoon (SIM) period.
- The NASA POWER air temperature data exhibited a noticeable shift, which was corrected by applying a simple bias correction method to each month's data, leading to a significant enhancement in correlation. This adjustment effectively addressed the discrepancy associated with a scaling factor, thereby improving the accuracy of the temperature data analysis.

- The NASA Power reanalysis wind speed data demonstrates a strong correlation with observed monthly values. This correlation highlights the reliability of the NASA Power data in representing wind speed patterns accurately.
- The NASA Power reanalysis data exhibits a robust correlation with observed values for relative humidity, except for deviations noted in January, February, and March.
- A comparison between observed cloud cover data and NASA Power reanalysis data revealed a strong correlation across all months, emphasizing the reliability of the NASA Power data in representing cloud cover patterns accurately.
- The General Lake Model (GLM) for daily lake surface water temperature demonstrated good performance during both calibration and validation phases, with a Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of 2.15 and 2.17, respectively, and correlation coefficients of 0.65 for both phases. The overall assessment combining both phases yielded an RMSE of 2.02 and a correlation coefficient of 0.73, indicating the model's accuracy across the dataset. This underscores the reliability of the GLM in predicting lake surface water temperature, essential for various environmental and climatological studies.
- Increased air temperature and solar radiation are the primary drivers of lake surface warming, while wind speed plays a critical mitigating role.

- The strong negative correlation between wind speed and temperature deviations (-0.87) highlights the importance of wind-driven mixing in regulating lake thermal dynamics.
- The scenario with a 5°C increase in air temperature, a 50% increase in solar radiation, a 50% decrease in wind speed, and a 50% decrease in rainfall is consistently dominant, demonstrating how reduced wind speeds and enhanced solar radiation synergistically drive surface temperature increases.
- The first and second inter-monsoon periods are highly sensitive to climatic changes, with April recording the peak deviation of 11.09°C.
- The southwest monsoon shows some buffering effects from increased rainfall and wind speeds, though warming persists due to elevated solar radiation and air temperatures.

5.2 Limitation with further studies

- Future studies should focus on conducting a detailed analysis utilizing comprehensive daily datasets to identify and correct the seasonal biases observed in precipitation and relative humidity. Enhanced methodologies that account for these biases will contribute significantly to the reliability of NASA Power Reanalysis data and its applications in environmental science and policymaking.

- Future research should focus on conducting a comprehensive analysis to identify and address the observed vertical shift in NASA Power reanalysis temperature data compared to the actual temperature measurements at the Nuwara Eliya station. This detailed study is essential for understanding the discrepancies between reanalysis products and ground observations, which can significantly impact climate modelling and environmental assessments in the region
- Future research should conduct a thorough analysis of the reliability of the LST-L2 product in comparison to observed lake surface temperatures across Sri Lanka. This investigation is essential for assessing the accuracy of satellite-derived temperature data, which can significantly influence environmental monitoring and management strategies.
- There are indications that the outflow may contribute to lower temperatures. However, due to the absence of documented evidence regarding the specific days or times of outlet openings, further investigation is necessary to delve deeper into this matter.
- Simplified Climatic Assumptions: The study used fixed increases in climatic variables without accounting for potential interdependencies between factors like air temperature, humidity, and cloud cover.

- Model Constraints: The lake model assumes steady-state conditions and not fully capture the complex interactions in real-world systems, such as nutrient dynamics and biological feedback.
- Incorporating Biological Feedbacks: Explore how thermal changes impact aquatic ecosystems, including stratification, oxygen levels, and biodiversity.

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ANNEX 01

Python code to extract observed climatic data from <https://en.tutiempo.net/climate>

```
import re
import requests
from bs4 import BeautifulSoup
import csv
from datetime import datetime, timedelta

# Function to generate the list of URLs
def generate_urls(start_date, end_date, base_url):
    urls = []
    current_date = start_date
    while current_date <= end_date:
        month = current_date.strftime("%m")
        year = current_date.strftime("%Y")
        url = f"{base_url}/{month}-{year}/ws-434730.html"
        urls.append((url, month, year))
        current_date += timedelta(days=32)
        current_date = current_date.replace(day=1)
    return urls

# Function to scrape and extract data from a given URL
def scrape_data(url, month, year):
    response = requests.get(url)
    soup = BeautifulSoup(response.content, "html.parser")

    # Locate the style block that contains the span class mappings
    style = soup.select_one('.medias').find_previous('style').string
    # Create a mapper from the style content using regex
    mapper = dict(re.findall(r'([\^.]?)::after{content:"(.*)"',
style))

    # Replace all <span class="..."> with their corresponding content
from the mapper
    for span in soup.find_all('span', class_=lambda cl: cl in
mapper):
```

```

        span.replace_with(mapper[span['class'][0]])

    # Find the table containing the climate data
    table_div = soup.find("div", class_="mt5 minoverflow tablanpcy")
    if not table_div:
        return None, None
    table = table_div.find("table", class_="medias mensuales
numspan")
    if not table:
        return None, None

    # Extract headers
    headers = ["Month", "Year"] + [header.text.strip() for header in
table.find_all("th")]
    rows = table.find_all("tr")[1:] # Skip the header row
    data = []

    # Extract data from each row
    for row in rows:
        cells = row.find_all("td")
        row_data = [month, year]
        for cell in cells:
            cell_text = cell.text.strip()
            if cell_text == '-' or cell_text == '':
                cell_text = '-'
            row_data.append(cell_text)
        while len(row_data) < 17: # Adjust for the extra columns
(Month and Year)
            row_data.append('')
        data.append(row_data)

    return headers, data

# Function to save data to CSV
def save_to_csv(headers, all_data, filename):
    with open(filename, mode='w', newline='', encoding='utf-8') as
file:
        writer = csv.writer(file)
        writer.writerow(headers)
        writer.writerows(all_data)
        print(f"Data saved to {filename}")

# Main function to scrape data from all URLs and save to CSV

```

```

def main():
    start_date = datetime(1990, 1, 1)
    end_date = datetime(2021, 12, 31)
    base_url = "https://en.tutiempo.net/climate"
    urls = generate_urls(start_date, end_date, base_url)

    all_data = []
    headers = None

    for url, month, year in urls:
        print(f"Scraping data from: {url}")
        try:
            headers, data = scrape_data(url, month, year)
            if headers and data:
                all_data.extend(data)
        except Exception as e:
            print(f"Failed to scrape {url}: {e}")

    if headers and all_data:
        save_to_csv(headers, all_data, "climate_data.csv")
    else:
        print("No data found")

# Run the main function
if __name__ == "__main__":
    main()

```

ANNEX 02

glm.nml file (uncalibrated)

```
&glm_setup
  sim_name = 'Gregorylake'
  max_layers = 500
  min_layer_vol = 0.0005
  min_layer_thick = 0.05
  max_layer_thick = 0.2
  density_model = 1
/
&light
  light_mode = 0
  Kw = 2.9
/
&mixing
  coef_mix_conv = 0.2
  coef_wind_stir = 0.3
  coef_mix_shear = 0.1
  coef_mix_turb = 0.45
  coef_mix_KH = 0.2
  coef_mix_hyp = 0.5
  deep_mixing = 1
  surface_mixing = 1
/
&morphometry
  lake_name = 'Gregorylake'
  latitude = 6.96
  longitude = 80.78
  crest_elev = 1873.58
  bsn_len = 1900
  bsn_wid = 900
  bsn_vals = 6
  H = 1871, 1871.5, 1872.08, 1872.5, 1873, 1873.58
  A = 4251.381, 43969.705, 148337.4, 236989.04, 304142.296, 481447.462
/
&time
  timefmt = 2
  start = '2017-01-01 12:00:00'
```

```

stop = '2021-12-31 12:00:00'
dt = 3600
num_days = 729
timezone = 5.5
/
&output
  out_dir = 'output'
  out_fn = 'output'
  nsave = 24
  csv_lake_fname = 'lake'
/
&init_profiles
  lake_depth = 2.58
  num_depths = 2
  the_depths = 1, 1.5
  the_temps = 20, 18
  the_sals = 0.5, 1.5
/
&meteorology
  met_sw = .true.
  lw_type = 'LW_CC'
  rain_sw = .false.
  atm_stab = 0
  catchrain = .true.
  rad_mode = 0
  albedo_mode = 2
  cloud_mode = 3
  fetch_mode = 0
  meteo_fl = 'bcs/met_data_nasa.csv'
  subdaily = .false.
  wind_factor = 1
  sw_factor = 1
  lw_factor = 1
  at_factor = 1
  rh_factor = 1
  rain_factor = 1
  cd = 0.0013
  ce = 0.0035
  ch = 0.0030
  rain_threshold = 0.025
  runoff_coef = 0.080
  time_fmt = 'YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss'
/
&sediment

```

```
sed_heat_Ksoil = 2.9
sed_temp_depth = 0.2
sed_temp_mean = 15,17,20
sed_temp_amplitude = 8,10,12
sed_temp_peak_doy = 130, 120, 110
benthic_mode = 1
n_zones = 3
zone_heights = 0.35, 0.6, 1.0
sed_reflectivity = 0.1, 0.01, 0.01
sed_roughness = 0.1, 0.01, 0.01
/
&bird_model
AP = 973
Oz = 0.279
WatVap = 1.1
AOD500 = 0.033
AOD380 = 0.038
Albedo = 0.2
/
```

ANNEX 03

GLM R Script to run model

```
cat("\f")
rm(list = ls())

setwd(dirname(rstudioapi::getSourceEditorContext())$path)
setwd('./glake')

list.files()

library(rLakeAnalyzer)
library(GLM3r)
library(glmtools)
library(tidyverse)
library(adagio)
library(ie2misc)
library(hydroGOF)
library(patchwork)

glm_version()

sim_folder <- getwd()
out_file <- file.path(sim_folder, "output", "output.nc")
nml_file <- file.path(sim_folder, 'glm3.nml')
glm_template = 'glm3-template.nml'
field_data <- file.path(sim_folder, "bcs", "Landsat_temp.csv")
Irrigation_data <- file.path(sim_folder, "bcs", "Irrigation_Temp.csv")

Sys.setenv(TZ='UTC')

GLM3r::run_glm(sim_folder, verbose = T)

# visualize change of surface water temp. over time
surface_temp <- get_var(file = out_file,
                        var_name = 'temp', reference = 'surface', z_out = 0)
```

```

ggplot(surface_temp, aes(DateTime, temp_0)) +
  geom_line() +
  ggtitle('Surface water temperature') +
  xlab(label = "") + ylab(label = 'Temp. (deg C)') +
  theme_minimal()

#average Temperature of simulation
mean(surface_temp$temp_0)

#Calculate RMSE value
temp_rmse <- compare_to_field(nc_file = out_file,
                             field_file = field_data,
                             metric = 'water.temperature',
                             as_value = FALSE,)

print(paste('Total time period (uncalibrated):',round(temp_rmse,2),'deg C RMSE'))

compare_data <- resample_to_field(nc_file = out_file, field_file = field_data,
                                 var_name = "temp")

compare_irrigation <- resample_to_field(nc_file = out_file, field_file = Irrigation_data,
                                       var_name = "temp")

write.csv(compare_irrigation, file.choose())
write.csv(compare_data, file.choose())
#correlation coefficient
cor(compare_data$Observed_temp, compare_data$Modeled_temp)

#write.csv(compare_data,file.choose())
#Replace Original Values
#file.copy(glm_template, 'glm3.nml', overwrite = TRUE)

#####
#
#Calibration
var = 'temp'    # variable to which we apply the calibration procedure
path = getwd()  # simulation path/folder
nml_file = nml_file # path of the nml configuration file that you want to calibrate on
glm_file = nml_file # # path of the gml configuration file

```

```

# which parameter do you want to calibrate? a sensitivity analysis helps
calib_setup <- data.frame('pars' =
  as.character(c('sed_temp_peak_doy','sed_temp_peak_doy','sed_temp_peak_doy',
                'ce','Kw','ch','sed_temp_depth',
                'sed_temp_mean','sed_temp_mean','sed_temp_mean',
                'sed_heat_Ksoil')),
  'lb' = c(60,110,100,
          0.0010,0.3,0.0030,0.2,
          15,15,15,
          1.0),
  'ub' = c(130,150,140,
          0.0035,2.9,0.0050,0.6,
          30,25,25,
          2.9),
  'x0' = c(130,120,110,
          0.0035,2.9,0.0030,0.2,
          15,17,20,
          2.9))
print(calib_setup)

glmcmd = NULL # command to be used, default applies the GLM3r function
# glmcmd = '/Users/robertladwig/Documents/AquaticEcoDynamics_gfort/GLM/glm' # custom path
# to executable
# Optional variables
first.attempt = TRUE # if TRUE, deletes all local csv-files that stores the
#outcome of previous calibration runs
period = get_calib_periods(nml_file, ratio = 0.665) # define a period for the calibration,
# this supports a split-sample calibration (e.g. calibration and validation period)
# the ratio value is the ratio of calibration period to validation period
print(period)
scaling = TRUE # scaling of the variables in a space of [0,10]; TRUE for CMA-ES
verbose = TRUE
method = 'CMA-ES' # optimization method, choose either `CMA-ES` or `Nelder-Mead`
metric = 'RMSE' # objective function to be minimized, here the root-mean square error
target.fit = 2.0 # refers to a target fit of 2.0 degrees Celsius (stops when RMSE is below that)
target.iter = 2000 # refers to a maximum run of 20 calibration iterations (stops after that many runs)
plotting = TRUE # if TRUE, script will automatically save the contour plots
output = out_file # path of the output file
field_file = field_data # path of the field data
conversion.factor = 1 # conversion factor for the output, e.g. 1 for water temp.

calibrate_sim(var = 'temp', path = getwd(),
             field_file = field_file,

```

```

    nml_file = nml_file,
    glm_file = glm_file,
    calib_setup = calib_setup,
    glmcmd = NULL, first.attempt = TRUE,
    period = period,
    scaling = TRUE, method = 'CMA-ES', metric = 'RMSE',
    target.fit = 2.0, target.iter = 2000,
    plotting = TRUE,
    output = output,
    verbose = FALSE,
    conversion.factor = 1)

# plot heat maps of water temperature
plot_var(nc_file = out_file, var_name = 'temp')

# visualize change of surface water temp. over time
surface_temp <- get_var(file = out_file,
    var_name = 'temp', reference = 'surface', z_out = 0)

ggplot(surface_temp, aes(DateTime, temp_0)) +
  geom_line() +
  ggtitle('Surface water temperature') +
  xlab(label = '') + ylab(label = 'Temp. (deg C)') +
  theme_minimal()

# Read observed temperature data from CSV file
observed_temp <- read.csv(field_data)

# Convert DateTime column to POSIXct class
observed_temp$datetime <- as.POSIXct(observed_temp$datetime)

ggplot(surface_temp, aes(DateTime, temp_0)) +
  geom_line() +
  geom_point(data = observed_temp, aes(datetime, temp), color = "red") +
  ggtitle('Surface water temperature') +
  xlab(label = '') + ylab(label = 'Temp. (deg C)') +
  theme_minimal()

# Read observed temperature data from Irrigation file
observed_temp_1 <- read.csv(Irrigation_data)

```

```

# Convert DateTime column to POSIXct class
observed_temp_1$datetime <- as.POSIXct(observed_temp_1$datetime)

ggplot(surface_temp, aes(DateTime, temp_0)) +
  geom_line() +
  geom_point(data = observed_temp_1, aes(datetime, temp), color = "red4") +
  geom_point(data = observed_temp, aes(datetime, temp), color = "red")+
  ggtitle('Surface water temperature') +
  xlab(label = "") + ylab(label = 'Temp. (deg C)') +
  theme_minimal()

ggplot(surface_temp, aes(DateTime, temp_0)) +
  geom_line() +
  geom_point(data = observed_temp, aes(datetime, temp), color = "red") +
  geom_line(data = observed_temp, aes(datetime, temp), color = "red") + # Add line for observed
values
  ggtitle('Surface water temperature') +
  xlab(label = "") + ylab(label = 'Temp. (deg C)') +
  theme_minimal()

# Read observed outflow data from outflow
Out_Flow <- read.csv("bcs/Outflow_Gregory.csv")

# Check the structure of the data frame to confirm column names
str(Out_Flow)

# Convert DateTime column to POSIXct class
Out_Flow$Date <- as.POSIXct(Out_Flow$Date)

# Check the range of dates in both datasets
min_date <- min(c(min(surface_temp$DateTime), min(observed_temp_1$datetime),
min(observed_temp$datetime), min(Out_Flow$Date)))
max_date <- max(c(max(surface_temp$DateTime), max(observed_temp_1$datetime),
max(observed_temp$datetime), max(Out_Flow$Date)))

# Plot for surface water temperature
temp_plot <- ggplot(surface_temp, aes(DateTime, temp_0)) +
  geom_line() +
  geom_point(data = observed_temp_1, aes(datetime, temp), color = "red4") +
  geom_point(data = observed_temp, aes(datetime, temp), color = "red") +
  ggtitle('Surface water temperature') +
  xlab(label = "") +

```

```

ylab(label = 'Temp. (deg C)') +
theme_minimal() +
xlim(min_date, max_date)

# Plot for outflow data
outflow_plot <- ggplot(Out_Flow, aes(Date, outflow)) + # Make sure the column name is correct
  geom_line(color = "blue") +
  ggtitle('Outflow Variation') +
  xlab('Date') +
  ylab('Flow (m3/s)') +
  theme_minimal() +
  xlim(min_date, max_date)

# Combine the two plots vertically
combined_plot <- temp_plot / outflow_plot

# Display the combined plot
print(combined_plot)

#Assuming you want a moving average over a window size of 5 data points
moving_avg <- surface_temp %>%
  mutate(ma_temp_0 = zoo::rollmean(temp_0, k = 10, fill = NA, align = "center"))

ggplot(surface_temp, aes(DateTime, temp_0)) +
  geom_line(color = "gray77") + # Plot the original surface_temp line in blue
  geom_point(data = observed_temp, aes(datetime, temp), color = "red") + # Plot observed
temperature points
  geom_line(data = observed_temp, aes(datetime, temp), color = "red") + # Add line for observed
values
  geom_line(data = moving_avg, aes(DateTime, ma_temp_0), color = "blue") + # Add moving average
line
  ggtitle('Surface water temperature') +
  xlab(label = "") + ylab(label = 'Temp. (deg C)') +
  theme_minimal()

```

ANNEX 04

```
# Clear the console and environment
cat("\f")
rm(list = ls())

# Set the working directory to the script's location and then move to the 'glake' directory
setwd(dirname(rstudioapi::getSourceEditorContext()$path))
setwd('./glake')

# Install required packages (comment out after first install)
#install.packages("devtools")
#require(devtools)
#devtools::install_github("robertladwig/GLM3r", ref = "v3.1.1")
#devtools::install_github("hdugan/glmtools", ref = "ggplot_overhaul")
#install.packages("rLakeAnalyzer")
#install.packages("tidyverse")

# List files in the working directory (optional)
list.files()

# Load necessary libraries
library(GLM3r)
library(glmtools)
library(ggplot2)
library(dplyr)
library(lubridate)

# Print the GLM version
glm_version()

# Define file paths
met_file_path <- "./met_data_nasa.csv"
nml_file_path <- "./glm3.nml"

# Check if base files exist
if (!file.exists(met_file_path)) stop("Error: met_data_nasa.csv not found.")
```

```

if (!file.exists(nml_file_path)) stop("Error: glm3.nml not found.")

# Define parameter ranges
air_temp_increases <- c(5, 2.5, -2.5, -5) #+5 OC (hot), +2.5 ~ (warm), -2.5 ~ (cool), to -5 ~
(cold)
shortwave_increases <- c(1.5, 1.25, 0.75, 0.5) #+50% (veryhigh-sunny), +25% (high), -25%
(low), and -50% (very low-cloudy).
wind_decreases <- c(1.5, 1.25, 0.75, 0.5)
rain_decreases <- c(1.5, 1.25, 0.75, 0.5)

# Create main scenario directory
dir.create("./activity_c_scenarios", showWarnings = FALSE)

# Load original meteorological data
metdata <- read.csv("met_data_nasa.csv")

# Initialize list to store surface temperature data
surf_temp <- list()

# Iterate over all parameter combinations
for (air_temp in air_temp_increases) {
  for (shortwave in shortwave_increases) {
    for (wind in wind_decreases) {
      for (rain in rain_decreases) {

        # Define scenario name and directory
        scenario_name <- paste0("air_", air_temp, "_shortwave_", shortwave, "_wind_",
wind, "_rain_", rain)
        scenario_dir <- paste0("./activity_c_scenarios/", scenario_name)
        dir.create(scenario_dir, showWarnings = FALSE)

        # Adjust meteorological data based on scenario
        scenario_metdata <- metdata
        scenario_metdata$AirTemp <- scenario_metdata$AirTemp + air_temp
        scenario_metdata$ShortWave <- scenario_metdata$ShortWave * shortwave
        scenario_metdata$WindSpeed <- scenario_metdata$WindSpeed * wind
        scenario_metdata$Rain <- scenario_metdata$Rain * rain
      }
    }
  }
}

```

```

# Save adjusted meteorological data
scenario_met_filepath <- paste0(scenario_dir, "/met_data_nasa.csv")
write.csv(scenario_metdata, scenario_met_filepath, row.names = FALSE, quote =
FALSE)

# Set up .nml file with scenario's meteorological file
scenario_nml_file <- file.path(paste0(scenario_dir, "/glm3.nml"))
file.copy("glm3.nml", scenario_nml_file, overwrite = TRUE)
scenario_nml <- glmtools::read_nml(nml_file = scenario_nml_file)
scenario_nml <- glmtools::set_nml(scenario_nml, arg_name = "meteo_fl", arg_val =
"met_data_nasa.csv")
glmtools::write_nml(scenario_nml, file = scenario_nml_file)

# Ensure the output directory exists
output_dir <- paste0(scenario_dir, "/output")
dir.create(output_dir, showWarnings = FALSE)

# Run GLM model for scenario
tryCatch({
  GLM3r::run_glm(sim_folder = scenario_dir, verbose = TRUE)
}, error = function(e) {
  message("Model run failed for scenario: ", scenario_name)
  next
})

# Define and check for the model output file
scenario_output_file <- file.path(scenario_dir, "output/output.nc")
if (file.exists(scenario_output_file)) {
  # Attempt to retrieve surface temperature output, with specific error handling
  tryCatch({
    scenario_temp <- get_var(file = scenario_output_file, "temp", reference =
"surface", z_out = 0)
    surf_temp[[scenario_name]] <- scenario_temp
  }, error = function(e) {
    message("Failed to retrieve data for scenario: ", scenario_name, " - ", e$message)
  })
} else {
  message("Output file not found for scenario: ", scenario_name)
}

```

```

    }
  }
}
}
}

# Generate a list of all expected scenario names
expected_scenarios <- c()
for (air_temp in air_temp_increases) {
  for (shortwave in shortwave_increases) {
    for (wind in wind_decreases) {
      for (rain in rain_decreases) {
        expected_scenarios <- c(expected_scenarios, paste0("air_", air_temp,
"_shortwave_", shortwave, "_wind_", wind, "_rain_", rain))
      }
    }
  }
}

# Identify which scenarios are missing from surf_temp
missing_scenarios <- setdiff(expected_scenarios, names(surf_temp))

# Print missing scenarios for investigation
if (length(missing_scenarios) > 0) {
  message("The following scenarios did not produce surface temperature data:")
  print(missing_scenarios)
} else {
  message("All scenarios produced surface temperature data.")
}

```

```

#####ReRun#####
#####

```

```

# Step 1: Identify scenarios expected to be in surf_temp
expected_scenario_names <- vector("character", length = 0)

```

```

# Loop through all combinations to generate the expected scenario names
for (air_temp in air_temp_increases) {
  for (shortwave in shortwave_increases) {
    for (wind in wind_decreases) {
      for (rain in rain_decreases) {
        scenario_name <- paste0("air_", air_temp, "_shortwave_", shortwave, "_wind_",
wind, "_rain_", rain)
        expected_scenario_names <- c(expected_scenario_names, scenario_name)
      }
    }
  }
}

```

```

# Step 2: Find missing scenarios (those not in surf_temp)
missing_scenarios <- setdiff(expected_scenario_names, names(surf_temp))
message("Missing scenarios (those without results in surf_temp):")
print(missing_scenarios)

```

```

# Step 3: Rerun missing scenarios and log details if they fail again
if (length(missing_scenarios) > 0) {
  for (scenario_name in missing_scenarios) {
    # Extract scenario parameters from the scenario name
    params <- strsplit(scenario_name, "_")[[1]]
    air_temp <- as.numeric(params[2])
    shortwave <- as.numeric(params[4])
    wind <- as.numeric(params[6])
    rain <- as.numeric(params[8])

```

```

# Define scenario directory
scenario_dir <- paste0("./activity_c_scenarios/", scenario_name)
dir.create(scenario_dir, showWarnings = FALSE)

```

```

# Adjust meteorological data based on scenario parameters
scenario_metdata <- metdata
scenario_metdata$AirTemp <- scenario_metdata$AirTemp + air_temp
scenario_metdata$ShortWave <- scenario_metdata$ShortWave * shortwave
scenario_metdata$WindSpeed <- scenario_metdata$WindSpeed * wind

```

```

scenario_metdata$Rain <- scenario_metdata$Rain * rain

# Save adjusted meteorological data
scenario_met_filepath <- paste0(scenario_dir, "/met_data_nasa.csv")
write.csv(scenario_metdata, scenario_met_filepath, row.names = FALSE, quote =
FALSE)

# Set up .nml file with scenario's meteorological file
scenario_nml_file <- file.path(scenario_dir, "/glm3.nml")
file.copy("glm3.nml", scenario_nml_file, overwrite = TRUE)
scenario_nml <- glmtools::read_nml(nml_file = scenario_nml_file)
scenario_nml <- glmtools::set_nml(scenario_nml, arg_name = "meteo_fl", arg_val =
"met_data_nasa.csv")
glmtools::write_nml(scenario_nml, file = scenario_nml_file)

# Ensure the output directory exists
output_dir <- paste0(scenario_dir, "/output")
dir.create(output_dir, showWarnings = FALSE)

# Run GLM model for the scenario
tryCatch({
  GLM3r::run_glm(sim_folder = scenario_dir, verbose = TRUE)
}, error = function(e) {
  message("Model run failed for missing scenario: ", scenario_name)
  return(NULL) # Skip to the next iteration if it fails
})

# Check for the model output file
scenario_output_file <- file.path(scenario_dir, "/output/output.nc")
if (file.exists(scenario_output_file)) {
  # Retrieve surface temperature output
  scenario_temp <- get_var(file = scenario_output_file, "temp", reference = "surface",
z_out = 0)
  surf_temp[[scenario_name]] <- scenario_temp
} else {
  message("Output file not found for missing scenario after rerun: ", scenario_name)
}
}

```

```

}

# Final check on surf_temp to ensure it has the expected number of elements
if (length(surf_temp) == length(expected_scenario_names)) {
  message("All scenarios successfully rerun and added to surf_temp.")
} else {
  message("Some scenarios still missing after rerun. Total scenarios in surf_temp: ",
length(surf_temp))
}

#####
#####
# Initialize an empty data frame to store temperature data across all scenarios
all_scenarios_df <- data.frame(DateTime = as.POSIXct(character()),
                               Temperature = numeric(),
                               Scenario = character())

# Loop through each scenario in surf_temp and add data to the combined data frame
for (scenario_name in names(surf_temp)) {
  scenario_data <- surf_temp[[scenario_name]]

  # Ensure DateTime is in POSIXct format
  scenario_data$DateTime <- as.POSIXct(scenario_data$DateTime)

  # Rename temp_0 to Temperature for consistency
  scenario_data <- scenario_data %>%
    rename(Temperature = temp_0) %>%
    mutate(Scenario = scenario_name) # Add a column for scenario name

  # Bind the data to the main data frame
  all_scenarios_df <- bind_rows(all_scenarios_df, scenario_data)
}

# Check structure of the combined data frame to ensure it has the right columns
str(all_scenarios_df)

# Sample plot for a few scenarios to verify

```

```

sample_scenarios <- unique(all_scenarios_df$Scenario)[1:5] # Use first 5 scenarios for
testing
sample_df <- all_scenarios_df %>% filter(Scenario %in% sample_scenarios)

ggplot(sample_df, aes(x = DateTime, y = Temperature, color = Scenario)) +
  geom_line() +
  ggtitle('Surface Water Temperature Over Time for Sample Scenarios') +
  xlab('Date') + ylab('Temperature (°C)') +
  theme_minimal() +
  theme(legend.position = "bottom")

# If the sample plot works, plot all scenarios
if (nrow(sample_df) > 0) {
  ggplot(all_scenarios_df, aes(x = DateTime, y = Temperature, color = Scenario)) +
    geom_line(alpha = 0.6) +
    ggtitle('Surface Water Temperature Over Time for All Scenarios') +
    xlab('Date') + ylab('Temperature (°C)') +
    theme_minimal() +
    theme(legend.position = "none") # Hide legend if there are too many scenarios
} else {
  message("No data to plot. Check if surf_temp contains valid scenario data.")
}

# Initialize an empty data frame to store temperature data across all scenarios
all_scenarios_df <- data.frame(DateTime = as.POSIXct(character()),
  Temperature = numeric(),
  Scenario = character())

# Initialize a vector to store the names of scenarios to exclude
excluded_scenarios <- c()

# Loop through each scenario in surf_temp and check for temperatures below 10°C
for (scenario_name in names(surf_temp)) {
  scenario_data <- surf_temp[[scenario_name]]

  # Check if any temperature values are below 10°C
  if (any(scenario_data$temp_0 < 10)) {

```

```

    excluded_scenarios <- c(excluded_scenarios, scenario_name) # Add to exclusion list
    next # Skip adding this scenario to the combined data frame
  }

  # Format DateTime as POSIXct and rename columns for consistency
  scenario_data$DateTime <- as.POSIXct(scenario_data$DateTime, tz = "UTC")
  scenario_data <- scenario_data %>%
    rename(Temperature = temp_0) %>%
    mutate(Scenario = scenario_name) # Add a column for scenario name

  # Add scenario data to the main data frame
  all_scenarios_df <- bind_rows(all_scenarios_df, scenario_data)
}

# Print the names of scenarios excluded due to low temperatures
if (length(excluded_scenarios) > 0) {
  message("Scenarios excluded due to surface temperatures below 10°C:")
  print(excluded_scenarios)
} else {
  message("No scenarios had surface temperatures below 10°C.")
}

#####ReRun EXculded#####

# Initialize an empty data frame to store temperature data across all scenarios
all_scenarios_df <- data.frame(DateTime = as.POSIXct(character()),
                               Temperature = numeric(),
                               Scenario = character())

# Initialize a vector to store the names of scenarios to exclude (those with temperatures
below 10°C)
excluded_scenarios <- c()

# Step 1: Filter out scenarios with temperatures below 10°C and store them in
all_scenarios_df
for (scenario_name in names(surf_temp)) {
  scenario_data <- surf_temp[[scenario_name]]

```

```

# Check if any temperature values are below 10°C
if (any(scenario_data$temp_0 < 10)) {
  excluded_scenarios <- c(excluded_scenarios, scenario_name) # Add to exclusion list
  next # Skip adding this scenario to the combined data frame
}

# Format DateTime as POSIXct and rename columns for consistency
scenario_data$DateTime <- as.POSIXct(scenario_data$DateTime, tz = "UTC")
scenario_data <- scenario_data %>%
  rename(Temperature = temp_0) %>%
  mutate(Scenario = scenario_name) # Add a column for scenario name

# Add scenario data to the main data frame
all_scenarios_df <- bind_rows(all_scenarios_df, scenario_data)
}

# Step 2: Print and rerun excluded scenarios if any
if (length(excluded_scenarios) > 0) {
  message("Rerunning scenarios excluded due to surface temperatures below 10°C:")
  print(excluded_scenarios)

  for (scenario_name in excluded_scenarios) {
    # Extract scenario parameters from the scenario name
    params <- strsplit(scenario_name, "_")[[1]]
    air_temp <- as.numeric(params[2])
    shortwave <- as.numeric(params[4])
    wind <- as.numeric(params[6])
    rain <- as.numeric(params[8])

    # Define scenario directory
    scenario_dir <- paste0("./activity_c_scenarios/", scenario_name)
    dir.create(scenario_dir, showWarnings = FALSE)

    # Adjust meteorological data based on scenario parameters
    scenario_metdata <- metdata
    scenario_metdata$AirTemp <- scenario_metdata$AirTemp + air_temp
    scenario_metdata$ShortWave <- scenario_metdata$ShortWave * shortwave
    scenario_metdata$WindSpeed <- scenario_metdata$WindSpeed * wind
  }
}

```

```

scenario_metdata$Rain <- scenario_metdata$Rain * rain

# Save adjusted meteorological data
scenario_met_filepath <- paste0(scenario_dir, "/met_data_nasa.csv")
write.csv(scenario_metdata, scenario_met_filepath, row.names = FALSE, quote =
FALSE)

# Set up .nml file with scenario's meteorological file
scenario_nml_file <- file.path(scenario_dir, "/glm3.nml")
file.copy("glm3.nml", scenario_nml_file, overwrite = TRUE)
scenario_nml <- glmtools::read_nml(nml_file = scenario_nml_file)
scenario_nml <- glmtools::set_nml(scenario_nml, arg_name = "meteo_fl", arg_val =
"met_data_nasa.csv")
glmtools::write_nml(scenario_nml, file = scenario_nml_file)

# Ensure the output directory exists
output_dir <- paste0(scenario_dir, "/output")
dir.create(output_dir, showWarnings = FALSE)

# Run GLM model for the scenario
tryCatch({
  GLM3r::run_glm(sim_folder = scenario_dir, verbose = TRUE)
}, error = function(e) {
  message("Model run failed for excluded scenario: ", scenario_name)
  next # Skip to the next scenario if it fails
})

# Check for the model output file
scenario_output_file <- file.path(scenario_dir, "/output/output.nc")
if (file.exists(scenario_output_file)) {
  # Retrieve surface temperature output
  scenario_temp <- get_var(file = scenario_output_file, "temp", reference = "surface",
z_out = 0)

  # Only add to surf_temp if all temperatures are above 10°C
  if (!any(scenario_temp$temp_0 < 10)) {
    surf_temp[[scenario_name]] <- scenario_temp
  }
}

```

```

# Format and add data to the main data frame
scenario_temp$DateTime <- as.POSIXct(scenario_temp$DateTime, tz = "UTC")
scenario_temp <- scenario_temp %>%
  rename(Temperature = temp_0) %>%
  mutate(Scenario = scenario_name)
all_scenarios_df <- bind_rows(all_scenarios_df, scenario_temp)
} else {
  message("Scenario still has temperatures below 10°C after rerun: ", scenario_name)
}
} else {
  message("Output file not found for excluded scenario after rerun: ", scenario_name)
}
}
} else {
message("No scenarios had surface temperatures below 10°C.")
}

# Final message indicating completion
message("Filtering and rerun process completed.")

#####

#####ReCheck below 10#####
# Initialize an empty data frame to store temperature data across all scenarios
all_scenarios_df <- data.frame(DateTime = as.POSIXct(character()),
  Temperature = numeric(),
  Scenario = character())

# Loop through each scenario in surf_temp and add data to the combined data frame
for (scenario_name in names(surf_temp)) {
  scenario_data <- surf_temp[[scenario_name]]

  # Ensure DateTime is in POSIXct format
  scenario_data$DateTime <- as.POSIXct(scenario_data$DateTime)

  # Rename temp_0 to Temperature for consistency
  scenario_data <- scenario_data %>%
    rename(Temperature = temp_0) %>%

```

```

mutate(Scenario = scenario_name) # Add a column for scenario name

# Bind the data to the main data frame
all_scenarios_df <- bind_rows(all_scenarios_df, scenario_data)
}

# Check structure of the combined data frame to ensure it has the right columns
str(all_scenarios_df)

# Sample plot for a few scenarios to verify
sample_scenarios <- unique(all_scenarios_df$Scenario)[1:5] # Use first 5 scenarios for
testing
sample_df <- all_scenarios_df %>% filter(Scenario %in% sample_scenarios)

ggplot(sample_df, aes(x = DateTime, y = Temperature, color = Scenario)) +
  geom_line() +
  ggtitle('Surface Water Temperature Over Time for Sample Scenarios') +
  xlab('Date') + ylab('Temperature (°C)') +
  theme_minimal() +
  theme(legend.position = "bottom")

# If the sample plot works, plot all scenarios
if (nrow(sample_df) > 0) {
  ggplot(all_scenarios_df, aes(x = DateTime, y = Temperature, color = Scenario)) +
    geom_line(alpha = 0.6) +
    ggtitle('Surface Water Temperature Over Time for All Scenarios') +
    xlab('Date') + ylab('Temperature (°C)') +
    theme_minimal() +
    theme(legend.position = "none") # Hide legend if there are too many scenarios
} else {
  message("No data to plot. Check if surf_temp contains valid scenario data.")
}

# Initialize an empty data frame to store temperature data across all scenarios
all_scenarios_df <- data.frame(DateTime = as.POSIXct(character()),
  Temperature = numeric(),
  Scenario = character())

```

```

# Initialize a vector to store the names of scenarios to exclude
excluded_scenarios <- c()

# Loop through each scenario in surf_temp and check for temperatures below 10°C
for (scenario_name in names(surf_temp)) {
  scenario_data <- surf_temp[[scenario_name]]

  # Check if any temperature values are below 10°C
  if (any(scenario_data$temp_0 < 10)) {
    excluded_scenarios <- c(excluded_scenarios, scenario_name) # Add to exclusion list
    next # Skip adding this scenario to the combined data frame
  }

  # Format DateTime as POSIXct and rename columns for consistency
  scenario_data$DateTime <- as.POSIXct(scenario_data$DateTime, tz = "UTC")
  scenario_data <- scenario_data %>%
    rename(Temperature = temp_0) %>%
    mutate(Scenario = scenario_name) # Add a column for scenario name

  # Add scenario data to the main data frame
  all_scenarios_df <- bind_rows(all_scenarios_df, scenario_data)
}

# Print the names of scenarios excluded due to low temperatures
if (length(excluded_scenarios) > 0) {
  message("Scenarios excluded due to surface temperatures below 10°C:")
  print(excluded_scenarios)
} else {
  message("No scenarios had surface temperatures below 10°C.")
}

#####
#####

#####Update All Senario DF#####

```

```

# Re-initialize surf_temp to hold updated data
surf_temp <- list()

# Loop through each scenario directory to read and extract surface temperature
scenario_dirs <- list.dirs(path = "./activity_c_scenarios", recursive = FALSE) # List scenario
directories

for (scenario_dir in scenario_dirs) {
  scenario_name <- basename(scenario_dir) # Extract scenario name from directory name

  # Define the path to the output NetCDF file
  output_file <- file.path(scenario_dir, "output/output.nc")

  # Check if the output file exists
  if (file.exists(output_file)) {
    # Try to retrieve surface temperature data
    tryCatch({
      # Extract surface temperature data at depth z = 0
      scenario_temp <- get_var(file = output_file, var_name = "temp", reference =
"surface", z_out = 0)

      # Store the data in surf_temp list under the scenario name
      surf_temp[[scenario_name]] <- scenario_temp
    }, error = function(e) {
      message("Failed to retrieve data for scenario: ", scenario_name)
    })
  } else {
    message("Output file not found for scenario: ", scenario_name)
  }
}

# Verify completion
#if (length(surf_temp) == length(scenario_dirs)) {
# message("All scenario data successfully updated in surf_temp.")
#} else {
# message("Some scenarios may still be missing in surf_temp.")
# message("Loaded scenarios: ", length(surf_temp), "/", length(scenario_dirs))
#}

```

```

all_scenarios_df <- data.frame(DateTime = as.POSIXct(character()),
                               Temperature = numeric(),
                               Scenario = character())

for (scenario_name in names(surf_temp)) {
  scenario_data <- surf_temp[[scenario_name]]

  # Ensure DateTime is in POSIXct format
  scenario_data$DateTime <- as.POSIXct(scenario_data$DateTime)

  # Rename temp_0 to Temperature for consistency
  scenario_data <- scenario_data %>%
    rename(Temperature = temp_0) %>%
    mutate(Scenario = scenario_name) # Add a column for scenario name

  # Bind the data to the main data frame
  all_scenarios_df <- bind_rows(all_scenarios_df, scenario_data)
}

# Check structure of the combined data frame to ensure it has the right columns
str(all_scenarios_df)

#####
# Set the expected number of rows for each scenario
expected_rows <- 1825

# Filter out scenarios with fewer rows than expected
filtered_surf_temp <- surf_temp[lapply(surf_temp, nrow) == expected_rows]

# Get the names of scenarios that were excluded
excluded_scenarios <- names(surf_temp)[lapply(surf_temp, nrow) != expected_rows]

# Print excluded scenarios
if (length(excluded_scenarios) > 0) {
  message("Scenarios excluded due to incomplete data:")
  print(excluded_scenarios)
} else {
  message("All scenarios have complete data.")
}

```

```

}
##### Re run for missing rows less than 1825#####

# Initialize list to store re-run scenario names
scenarios_to_rerun <- names(surf_temp)[lapply(surf_temp, nrow) != expected_rows]

# Print scenarios to re-run
if (length(scenarios_to_rerun) > 0) {
  message("Scenarios to re-run due to incomplete data:")
  print(scenarios_to_rerun)
} else {
  message("No incomplete scenarios found. All scenarios have 1825 rows.")
}

# Loop through and re-run scenarios
for (scenario_name in scenarios_to_rerun) {
  scenario_dir <- file.path("./activity_c_scenarios", scenario_name)
  scenario_met_filepath <- file.path(scenario_dir, "met_data_nasa.csv")
  scenario_nml_file <- file.path(scenario_dir, "glm3.nml")
  scenario_output_file <- file.path(scenario_dir, "output/output.nc")

  # Ensure necessary files exist before re-running
  if (file.exists(scenario_met_filepath) && file.exists(scenario_nml_file)) {
    tryCatch({
      # Ensure output directory exists
      dir.create(file.path(scenario_dir, "output"), showWarnings = FALSE)

      # Run GLM model for the scenario
      GLM3r::run_glm(sim_folder = scenario_dir, verbose = TRUE)

      # Verify if output was generated
      if (file.exists(scenario_output_file)) {
        # Update surf_temp with the new output
        scenario_temp <- get_var(file = scenario_output_file, var_name = "temp", reference
= "surface", z_out = 0)
        surf_temp[[scenario_name]] <- scenario_temp
      } else {
        message("Failed to generate output for scenario: ", scenario_name)
      }
    }, error = function(e) {
      message("Error running GLM model for scenario: ", scenario_name, ": ", e$message)
    })
  }
}

```

```

    }
  }, error = function(e) {
    message("Model run failed for scenario: ", scenario_name)
  })
} else {
  message("Required files missing for scenario: ", scenario_name)
}
}

# Check for updated data
if (all(lapply(surf_temp, nrow) == expected_rows)) {
  message("All scenarios now have complete data.")
} else {
  message("Some scenarios still have incomplete data.")
}

#####
# Plot the scenarios with ggplot2
ggplot(all_scenarios_df, aes(x = DateTime, y = Temperature, color = Scenario)) +
  geom_line(alpha = 0.6) +
  ggtitle('Surface Water Temperature Over Time') +
  xlab('Date') + ylab('Temperature (°C)') +
  theme_minimal() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") # Hide legend if there are too many scenarios

# Ensure DateTime is properly formatted with a valid timezone
all_scenarios_df <- all_scenarios_df %>%
  mutate(DateTime = as.POSIXct(DateTime, tz = "UTC"))

# Calculate monthly averages
all_scenarios_monthly <- all_scenarios_df %>%
  mutate(YearMonth = floor_date(DateTime, "month")) %>% # Extract year and month
  group_by(Scenario, YearMonth) %>%
  summarize(MonthlyAvgTemp = mean(Temperature, na.rm = TRUE)) %>%
  ungroup()

```

```

# Plot the monthly averages for each scenario
ggplot(all_scenarios_monthly, aes(x = YearMonth, y = MonthlyAvgTemp, color =
Scenario)) +
  geom_line(alpha = 0.7) +
  ggtitle('Monthly Average Surface Water Temperature for All Scenarios') +
  xlab('Date') + ylab('Temperature (°C)') +
  theme_minimal() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") # Hide legend if too many scenarios

# Define baseline file path
baseline_nc_file <- file.path("./output/output.nc")

# Ensure the baseline file exists
if (!file.exists(baseline_nc_file)) {
  stop("Baseline .nc file not found in './glake/output/'.")
}

# Extract surface temperature for the baseline
baseline_temp <- get_var(file = baseline_nc_file, var_name = "temp", reference =
"surface", z_out = 0)

# Format baseline temperature for plotting
baseline_temp <- baseline_temp %>%
  mutate(DateTime = as.POSIXct(DateTime, tz = "UTC"),
    Scenario = "Baseline") %>%
  rename(Temperature = temp_0)

# Combine all scenario data with the baseline
all_data_with_baseline <- bind_rows(all_scenarios_df, baseline_temp)

# Plot all scenarios with baseline in black
ggplot(all_data_with_baseline, aes(x = DateTime, y = Temperature, color = Scenario)) +
  geom_line(alpha = 0.6) + # Scenarios
  geom_line(data = baseline_temp, # Baseline in black
    aes(x = DateTime, y = Temperature),
    color = "black", size = 1.2) +
  ggtitle('Surface Water Temperature Over Time') +
  xlab('Date') + ylab('Temperature (°C)') +

```

```

theme_minimal() +
theme(legend.position = "none") # Hide legend if too many scenarios

# Calculate monthly averages for the baseline
baseline_monthly <- baseline_temp %>%
  mutate(YearMonth = floor_date(DateTime, "month")) %>%
  group_by(YearMonth) %>%
  summarize(MonthlyAvgTemp = mean(Temperature, na.rm = TRUE))

# Combine all scenario monthly averages with the baseline monthly average
all_monthly_with_baseline <- bind_rows(all_scenarios_monthly,
  baseline_monthly %>% mutate(Scenario = "Baseline"))

# Plot all monthly averages with baseline in black
ggplot(all_monthly_with_baseline, aes(x = YearMonth, y = MonthlyAvgTemp, color =
Scenario)) +
  geom_line(alpha = 0.7) + # Scenarios
  geom_line(data = baseline_monthly, # Baseline in black
    aes(x = YearMonth, y = MonthlyAvgTemp),
    color = "black", size = 1.2) +
  ggtitle('Monthly Average Surface Water Temperature for All Scenarios') +
  xlab('Date') + ylab('Temperature (°C)') +
  theme_minimal() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") # Hide legend if too many scenarios

#####

# Combine baseline monthly averages with scenario monthly averages
all_monthly_with_baseline <- all_scenarios_df %>%
  mutate(Month = month(DateTime, label = TRUE)) %>%
  group_by(Scenario, Month) %>%
  summarize(MonthlyAvgTemp = mean(Temperature, na.rm = TRUE)) %>%
  ungroup()

baseline_monthly_avg <- baseline_temp %>%
  mutate(Month = month(DateTime, label = TRUE)) %>%
  group_by(Month) %>%
  summarize(BaselineAvgTemp = mean(Temperature, na.rm = TRUE)) %>%

```

```

ungroup()

# Join baseline averages with scenario averages
monthly_comparison <- all_monthly_with_baseline %>%
  left_join(baseline_monthly_avg, by = "Month") %>%
  mutate(TempDeviation = MonthlyAvgTemp - BaselineAvgTemp)

# Plot histogram of temperature deviations
ggplot(monthly_comparison, aes(x = TempDeviation, fill = Scenario)) +
  geom_histogram(binwidth = 0.1, position = "identity", alpha = 0.6) +
  ggtitle("Histogram of Average Monthly Temperature Deviations (Scenarios vs.
Baseline)") +
  xlab("Temperature Deviation (°C)") +
  ylab("Frequency") +
  theme_minimal()

# Filter scenarios with maximum deviations
max_deviation_scenarios <- monthly_comparison %>%
  group_by(Scenario) %>%
  summarize(MaxDeviation = max(abs(TempDeviation))) %>%
  arrange(desc(MaxDeviation))

# Print top scenarios with maximum climate change effect
message("Top scenarios with maximum deviations:")
print(max_deviation_scenarios)

# Highlight the most extreme scenarios in the histogram
extreme_scenarios <- max_deviation_scenarios %>% top_n(10, MaxDeviation)

ggplot(monthly_comparison %>% filter(Scenario %in% extreme_scenarios$Scenario),
  aes(x = TempDeviation, fill = Scenario)) +
  geom_histogram(binwidth = 0.1, position = "identity", alpha = 0.6) +
  ggtitle("Top Scenarios with Maximum Temperature Deviations") +
  xlab("Temperature Deviation (°C)") +
  ylab("Frequency") +
  theme_minimal()

# Check the range of TempDeviation

```

```

summary(monthly_comparison$TempDeviation)

# Filter out rows with missing or zero deviations
monthly_comparison_filtered <- monthly_comparison %>%
  filter(!is.na(TempDeviation), TempDeviation != 0)

# Plot histogram with adjusted bin width
ggplot(monthly_comparison_filtered, aes(x = TempDeviation, fill = Scenario)) +
  geom_histogram(binwidth = 0.05, position = "identity", alpha = 0.6) +
  ggtitle("Histogram of Average Monthly Temperature Deviations (Scenarios vs.
Baseline)") +
  xlab("Temperature Deviation (°C)") +
  ylab("Frequency") +
  theme_minimal() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") # Adjust legend placement

# Optional: Add density plot if histogram remains unclear
ggplot(monthly_comparison_filtered, aes(x = TempDeviation, color = Scenario)) +
  geom_density(alpha = 0.7) +
  ggtitle("Density Plot of Temperature Deviations") +
  xlab("Temperature Deviation (°C)") +
  ylab("Density") +
  theme_minimal() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") # Hide legend for clarity

#####

# Extract the month from YearMonth for easier grouping
#monthly_comparison <- monthly_comparison %>%
# mutate(Month = format(YearMonth, "%B"))

# Identify the scenario with the most effect for each month
most_effective_scenarios <- monthly_comparison %>%
  group_by(Month) %>%
  summarize(
    Scenario = Scenario[which.max(TempDeviation)],
    MaxDeviation = max(TempDeviation)
  ) %>%

```

```

arrange(match(Month, month.name)) # Order months from January to December

# Print the summary table
print(most_effective_scenarios)

# Optional: Visualize the most effective scenarios
ggplot(most_effective_scenarios, aes(x = Month, y = MaxDeviation, fill = Scenario)) +
  geom_bar(stat = "identity") +
  ggtitle("Scenarios with the Maximum Temperature Deviation by Month") +
  xlab("Month") +
  ylab("Maximum Temperature Deviation (°C)") +
  theme_minimal() +
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1)) +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(title = "Scenario"))

# Identify the scenario with the minimum effect for each month
least_effective_scenarios <- monthly_comparison %>%
  group_by(Month) %>%
  summarize(
    Scenario = Scenario[which.min(TempDeviation)],
    MinDeviation = min(TempDeviation)
  ) %>%
  arrange(match(Month, month.name)) # Order months from January to December

# Print the summary table
print(least_effective_scenarios)

# Optional: Visualize the least effective scenarios
ggplot(least_effective_scenarios, aes(x = Month, y = MinDeviation, fill = Scenario)) +
  geom_bar(stat = "identity") +
  ggtitle("Scenarios with the Minimum Temperature Deviation by Month") +
  xlab("Month") +
  ylab("Minimum Temperature Deviation (°C)") +
  theme_minimal() +
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1)) +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(title = "Scenario"))

```

```

# Identify the scenario with the 1st quantile effect for each month
first_quantile_scenarios <- monthly_comparison %>%
  group_by(Month) %>%
  summarize(
    Scenario = Scenario[which.min(abs(TempDeviation - quantile(TempDeviation, 0.25)))],
    FirstQuantileDeviation = quantile(TempDeviation, 0.25)
  ) %>%
  arrange(match(Month, month.name)) # Order months from January to December

# Print the summary table
print(first_quantile_scenarios)

# Optional: Visualize the first quantile scenarios
ggplot(first_quantile_scenarios, aes(x = Month, y = FirstQuantileDeviation, fill = Scenario))
+
  geom_bar(stat = "identity") +
  ggtitle("Scenarios with the 1st Quantile Temperature Deviation by Month") +
  xlab("Month") +
  ylab("1st Quantile Temperature Deviation (°C)") +
  theme_minimal() +
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1)) +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(title = "Scenario"))

# Identify the scenario with the 2nd quantile (Median) effect for each month
second_quantile_scenarios <- monthly_comparison %>%
  group_by(Month) %>%
  summarize(
    Scenario = Scenario[which.min(abs(TempDeviation - quantile(TempDeviation, 0.50)))],
    SecondQuantileDeviation = quantile(TempDeviation, 0.50)
  ) %>%
  arrange(match(Month, month.name)) # Order months from January to December

# Print the summary table
print(second_quantile_scenarios)

# Optional: Visualize the second quantile scenarios
ggplot(second_quantile_scenarios, aes(x = Month, y = SecondQuantileDeviation, fill =
Scenario)) +

```

```

geom_bar(stat = "identity") +
ggtitle("Scenarios with the 2nd Quantile (Median) Temperature Deviation by Month") +
xlab("Month") +
ylab("2nd Quantile Temperature Deviation (°C)") +
theme_minimal() +
theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1)) +
guides(fill = guide_legend(title = "Scenario"))

# Identify the scenario with the 3rd quantile (75th percentile) effect for each month
third_quantile_scenarios <- monthly_comparison %>%
  group_by(Month) %>%
  summarize(
    Scenario = Scenario[which.min(abs(TempDeviation - quantile(TempDeviation, 0.75)))],
    ThirdQuantileDeviation = quantile(TempDeviation, 0.75)
  ) %>%
  arrange(match(Month, month.name)) # Order months from January to December

# Print the summary table
print(third_quantile_scenarios)

# Optional: Visualize the third quantile scenarios
ggplot(third_quantile_scenarios, aes(x = Month, y = ThirdQuantileDeviation, fill =
Scenario)) +
  geom_bar(stat = "identity") +
  ggtitle("Scenarios with the 3rd Quantile (75th Percentile) Temperature Deviation by
Month") +
  xlab("Month") +
  ylab("3rd Quantile Temperature Deviation (°C)") +
  theme_minimal() +
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1)) +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(title = "Scenario"))

# Identify the scenario with the mean temperature deviation for each month
mean_scenarios <- monthly_comparison %>%
  group_by(Month) %>%
  summarize(
    Scenario = Scenario[which.min(abs(TempDeviation - mean(TempDeviation, na.rm =
TRUE)))],

```

```

    MeanDeviation = mean(TempDeviation, na.rm = TRUE)
  ) %>%
  arrange(match(Month, month.name)) # Order months from January to December

# Print the summary table
print(mean_scenarios)

# Optional: Visualize the mean scenarios
ggplot(mean_scenarios, aes(x = Month, y = MeanDeviation, fill = Scenario)) +
  geom_bar(stat = "identity") +
  ggtitle("Scenarios with Mean Temperature Deviation by Month") +
  xlab("Month") +
  ylab("Mean Temperature Deviation (°C)") +
  theme_minimal() +
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1)) +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(title = "Scenario"))

```

ANNEX 05

Office of the Zonal Director of Irrigation - Central Zone

Water Quality Monitoring Unit

Gregory Lake																			
Date	2017		2018		2019						2020					2021			
	20.03.2017	20.09.2017	20.02.2018	31.07.2018	31.01.2019			04.07.2019			29.09.2020					23.02.2021			
Location	Tank	Tank	Tank	Tank	Tank	Near Spill (Podi Wewa)	Inlet	Tank (near the Boat Jetty)	Sluice	Inlet	Tank - Point 1	Tank - Point 2	Near the Sluice	Near the Spill	Inlet	Tank - Point 1	Tank - Point 2	Sluice	Inlet
PH	7.93	6.52	6.84	5.92	7.03	7.44	6.90	9.06	8.08	7.67	8.12	8.05	8.10	8.12	7.97	10.08	9.79	10.35	8.77
Temperature	23.0	23.0	22.0	17.0	23.0	23.0	23.0	21.0	21.0	21.0	16.0	16.0	16.0	16.0	16.0	21.9	21.4	20.9	19.7
Conductivity	191.60	140.40	188.20	101.80	164.30	167.00	200.70	191.70	193.70	285.00	98.50	91.70	97.00	94.00	101.70	126.80	112.40	132.20	6.72
Turbidity	17.50	23.60	37.40	27.70	31.10	21.50	11.20	142.00	107.00	11.30	12.80	22.40	8.65	7.34	2.90	32.20	47.40	21.10	4.58
DO	8.41	7.49	3.03	7.12	7.62	7.61	2.19	5.98	5.25	1.91	7.29	8.14	8.43	8.12	5.24	12.04	8.56	11.07	1.79
COD	-	113	-	-	-	30	34	117	93	17	27	14	21	15	5	-	-	-	-
BOD	12.0	-	-	-	-	21.0	-	-	13.0	-	-	-	22.0	-	-	20.0	-	26.0	-
Nitrate / NO ₃ ⁻	1.4	2.0	6.4	2.3	0.0	0.0	2.1	0.0	0.0	1.5	7.7	11.7	6.3	6.2	4.8	0.9	1.2	0.0	1.0
Phosphate / PO ₄ ⁻³	1.02	0.07	0.33	0.08	0.16	0.17	1.02	0.15	0.17	1.01	0.07	0.38	0.06	0.09	0.16	0.12	0.07	0.05	0.12
Sulfate / SO ₄ ²⁻	17	10	7	6	7	7	6	7	7	5	4	6	6	7	5	2	2	2	0
UIA	0.0251	0.000104	0.000414	0.000117	0.000864	0.00057	0.01426	0.03768	0.00438	0.11098	0.009345	0.007722	0.006675	0.000445	0.005148	-	-	-	-
Fe	7.0	0.34	0.49	0.53	0.51	0.40	2.59	0.91	0.69	2.35	0.36	0.64	0.33	0.31	0.33	0.55	0.40	0.13	0.13
Total Alkalinity (as CaCO ₃)	-	301.0	-	245.0	47.8	48.0	3.2	30.8	33.6	82.4	-	-	-	-	-	166.0	124.0	126.0	76.0
Hardness (as CaCO ₃)	25.0	68.0	-	-	-	-	-	320.0	184.0	124.0	-	-	-	-	-	40.40	34.00	54.00	14.80